

The Peer Review Cult “cover-up”: Conspiracy Facts the ‘fact-checkers’ do not want you to know about.

Reaction to news about the ‘Vampire Star’ and the truth about Z-pinch fusion and a rebuttal to Shermer’s Article about the Electric Universe; plus Information on the US Biolabs, COVID coverup, and more.

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Best Viewed At: <https://bit.ly/3tkUrRy>

ABSTRACT

The author sets forth to critique the critics of the Electric Universe, and in reaction to revelations about fusion and the fictional black hole “Vampire Star,” to set forth a convincing narrative that hits the peer review cult hardest where it deserves it: lies by omission. While not a conclusive study into the issue, the author cites numerous failings of the peer review community as yet unaddressed by Science and its guardians of the cult. Scientism is a serious ethical and scientific problem, and the author spends some time in responding to one major name in the game of “controlled opposition”: Dr. M. Shermer, “Skeptic Magazine.” by showing the problems in his article and line of argumentation, as well as outlining a clearly different path for superior cosmologies (EU and EPEMC¹), the author encourages the reader to think about the line of evidence (both mainstream and altstream) and consider for themselves, who is more trustworthy? Especially in the face of events since 2015.

Key Words: Shermer - Electric Universe - Vampire Star - M87 - Fusion - peer-review - crisis - cosmology

¹ Electric Universe and Extended Plasma-Electromagnetic Cosmology, respectively

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The Peer Review Cult vs. Skepticism

Some years ago, The Thunderbolts Project people, primarily Walt and Dave, were gracious enough, and even excited (albeit maybe naive) to invite Dr. Michael Shermer to the Electric Universe Conference². Now this altstream conference is about as mainstream-like as you can get. All of the talks at the conference are scientific, and couched in evidence, with minimal (but usually appropriate) conjecture. The Electric Universetm, in general, is couched in an anti-alien, anti-flat Earth, even anti-Atlantology and agnostic position. The most 'weird' that they get is to discuss if stars have consciousness³, and the bizarre behaviors of water⁴.

The EU 2015 Conference⁵

This is a list of the conference lineup⁶:

1. Wallace Thornhill, engineer and physicist, advisor to SAFIRE phases 1 & 2
"The Long Path to Understanding Gravity"
2. David Talbot, author, comparative mythologist, writer of "Saturn Theory"
"Cultural Quandaries" (a talk about the transformations of mythic archetypes over time)
3. Dr. Donald Scott, electrical engineer, emeritus, author "The Electric Sun"
"Cosmic Power Lines" (a talk about filamentary transfer and counter-rotation in Birkeland Currents in atmospheric evidence)
4. Montgomery Childs, lead engineer and project director SAFIRE project
"SAFIRE Project Update"
5. Ben Davidson, JD, lawyer and community activist⁷, author of "the Weatherman's Guide to the Sun"
"Does the Sun Trigger Large Earthquakes?"
"An Introduction to Earthspots" (a talk about low pressure zones and blot echo earthquakes)
6. Dr. Gerald Pollack, professor of bioengineering
"Beyond Water: What Makes the World Go Round?" (a talk about the fourth phase of water, with negative charge)
7. Dr. Michael Clarage, electrical engineer and cosmologist, second lead at project SAFIRE
"SAFIRE and the Electric Sun Model"
8. Dr. Lowell Morgan, Plasma/HEP physicist
"The Physics of Plasma" (a talk about SAFIRE phase 1 paper)
9. Dr. Paul Anderson, Chemist
"Statistics to Save Us from Data Overload" (relates to Dr. Anderson's talk)
10. Dr. Kongpop U-yen, electrical engineer
"Solar System Formation, Quantum Vibration, and Natural Disasters"

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SI6xKcO3ufs>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KZonJAYwtiA>

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KnwAUVNhU0s&list=PLwOAYhBuU3Uf9f87W3Wr3tCqsOgy91q4u>

⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6J3wVYZCeGI&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UfCD_3S2i8x3dI-mLbU1YCD

⁶ <https://www.thunderbolts.info/wp/2015/01/31/eu2015-speakers/>

⁷ <https://otf.selz.com> & <https://www.SuspiciousObservers.org>

11. Jano Onderco, master's in Technical Cybernetics, specialty in Special Relativity, software and project management
"SAFIRE Instrumentation, Data Collection, and Correlation"
12. Dr. Michael Shermer, "Skeptic Magazine"
"Distinguishing Science from Pseudoscience"*
13. Dr. Gary Schwartz, a professor of psychology, medicine, neurology, psychiatry and surgery, and a Harvard graduate
"Extraordinary Ideas and Extraordinary Evidence: The Fiver Finger Test"
14. Dr. Andrew Bartlett, sociologist, biologist, geneticist
"The Sociology of Science: Consensus and Controversies"***
15. Dr. C J Ransom, plasma physicist
"Close Encounter of the Star Kind and the Conehead Connection"
"Surprising Solar System"
16. Dr. Franklin Anariba, electrochemist and biomedical applications
"Electrochemistry of Comets: An Update"
17. Dr. Tom Wilson, botanist and semiconductor expert
"When the Surprise is Unsurprising: the Siren Song of Certainty"
18. Eugene Bagashov, physicist and philosopher
"Creator's Second Hand" (a talk about coriolis effect, magnus force, and Lorentz force)
19. Bruce Leybourne, geologist and research director
"Earth as a Stellar Transformer: Climate Change Revealed"
20. Annis Scott, author
"The Paths to Discovering Our Universe, Past and Present"
21. Dr. A P David, classical Hellenistic scholar
"The Metaphysics of Michael Faraday"
22. Ev Cochrane, comparative mythologist and author
"Planetary Catastrophe, Ancient Myths, & Modern Science"
23. Dr. Pierre-Marie Robitaille, spectroscopist and professor
"Kirchoff's Claims" (a talk about the failure of Kirchoff's Law)
24. Stephen Crothers, mathematician
"General Relativity:A Case Study in Numerology"
25. Dr. Robert L. Straitt ,applied sciences, manufacturing, defense etc.
"Revisiting Our Understanding of Classical Physics and Relativity"
26. Michael Steinbacher, journalist, photographer, and electro-geology enthusiast
"Plasma Catastrophist Geology"
27. Richard Moore, mathematician
"The Pulsating Universe and Planet Earth"
28. Arthur Ramthun, engineer
"Plant Electro-tropism" (a unique talk about measured plant electric current***)
29. Michael Armstrong, chemist
"The 'Culture Shock' of Planetary Catastrophe"
30. Dwardu Cardona, author, KRONOS editor
"Order Out of Chaos" (basically a talk about Genesis)

31. Master of ceremonies: educator and author David Novak

Clearly one can see: no alien or flat-earth pseudoscientist on board.

* - The irony of this is dripping

** - This is the person more likely to be able to talk about the topic Shermer gave

*** - Shermer leaving out this topic in his rant article really shows how disingenuous he is to this list of preeminent men and one woman. Literally a whole realm of industrial applications comes from this talk alone.

On top of this, they even had an open panel, were warm, and allowed him to make his subtle jabs at them without negative comment.⁸ Nevertheless, afterwards as is predictable, this mainstream shill and fake skeptic known as Michael Shermer, wrote a dark, sinister, character-sniping article⁹, and sent it out into the peer review community as a form of virtue signaling¹⁰. It had no virtue. Nevertheless, let us recall some of the more gutless comments (numbers added are my own):

Quotes from Shermer's Article, Finally Dealt With

“(1) Newton was wrong. Einstein was wrong. Black holes do not exist. The big bang never happened. Dark energy and dark matter are unsubstantiated conjectures. Stars are electrically charged plasma masses. Venus was once a comet. (2) The massive Valles Marineris canyon on Mars was carved out in a few minutes by a giant electric arc sweeping across the Red Planet. (3) The “thunderbolt” icons found in ancient art and petroglyphs are not the iconography of imagined gods but realistic representations of spectacular electrical activity in space.”

1. Well, in a strict sense, we (all of us scientists) are wrong, because the model is **never** complete. But setting aside the fractal nature of the Universe, in a literal sense Newton was definitely wrong and Einstein was a thief.
As for black holes, there are holes that are without visible light, but there are no classical black hole objects, and that's now known. The next two sentences are proven facts, so no need to reply to that. And Venus was, indeed, once a comet and we have measured its plasma tail.
2. That's a hypothesis, but it is the best hypothesis by far because it has eyewitness and visible evidence.
3. This is a fact and proven with laboratory science. Not sure what his beef is with using glyphic evidence, but based upon the Chinese etymology we now know Dr. Peratt was onto something more than anyone. Which is why Dr. Robert Schoch, geologist, is also onto it now.¹¹

“(4) I was invited to speak on the difference between science and pseudoscience. The most common theme I gleaned from the conference is that one should be skeptical of all

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r4r4nvda4LY>

⁹ <https://michaelshermer.com/sciam-columns/the-electric-universe-acid-test/>

¹⁰ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/the-difference-between-science-and-pseudoscience/>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PUqdYBxbck>

things mainstream: cosmology, physics, history, psychology and (5) even government (6)(I was told that World Trade Center Building 7 was brought down by controlled demolition on 9/11 and (7) that “chemtrails”—the contrails in the sky trailing jets—are evidence of a government climate-engineering experiment).”

4. That’s a bit of a laugh because Shermer cannot succinctly define it as we shall see in point 16-18. What I’d like to focus on is why a paid ‘skeptic’ wouldn’t want to be skeptical? Hmm, perhaps my hypothesis is already panning out.
5. Anyone not skeptical of the government has failed history 101 class. The entire 20th century reads as a study in failed governments and economic disasters, genocides, and wars. As this author predicted our New Cold War and we now have a new Iron Curtain and threat of nuclear attack, he feels justified in saying most assuredly that the statements made by Shermer here are not only negligent and nescient, they are harmful to the Truth.
6. This is a fact of evidence and chronology. But more importantly the way he lobs this in here as a general smear is incredibly pathetic and detestable.
7. Chemtrails are also a fact and in the final part I will produce some of the declassified documents regarding the issue. In fact based on points 4-7 let’s just bust open the entire top secret science and government mind-control factbook.

“The acid test of a scientific claim, I explained,(8) is prediction and falsification. My friends at the NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory, for example, tell me they use both (9) Newtonian mechanics and Einstein’s relativity theory in computing highly accurate spacecraft trajectories to the planets.”

8. So theoretically he understands skepticism. However, the EU theorists and Velikovsky made these predictions, and have been vilified for them. Particularly Velikovsky. Sagan went on to make an ‘apology’ for the Velikovsky affair, and to basically say we cannot allow non-scientists to challenge science. But Velikovsky was a scientist as well, and produced a wonderfully lucid document on gravitation, or more specifically “Cosmos without Gravitation,” which was without refute.

As for falsification, we cannot trust - or even allow - the mainstream of science to alter the Standard Model, it is has shown itself to be two-faced, double-speaking, irrational, emotional, and most of all fraudulent (in stealing credit, for one thing, and falsifying data for the other).

9. Of course these are used, but primarily they use Kepler’s Laws of Motion. So the mechanics point is moot and the relativity point has little merit. We don’t send craft into space at relativistic speeds. So it’s an unprovable and unproven statement, made out of context. Not surprising.

“No, he replied. GPS satellites in orbit around Earth are also dependent on relativity theory, so I asked the conference host David Talbott if EU theory offers anything like the practical applications that theoretical physics has given us. (10) No. Then what does EU theory add? A deeper understanding of nature, I was told. (11) Oh.”

10. Well, the author is not sure what Dave said, but he’d have to disagree with him if he said no. Then again, EPEMC is far more engineered to be of practical use

than the EU. At any rate in EPEMC we do not deny quantum mechanics, chemistry progress, etc. Electrogeology has many practical future applications, but needs a large amount of lab work done by professionals. But plasma labs do practical things all the time. This is a petty point to compare what amounts to a dozen or so guys with long careers, some of them in engineering, with a huge body of scientists getting government contracts. If the author received a \$10 billion grant, he could literally change the world.

11. This is such a disingenuous smear. First it implies there's nothing useful about improved philosophy, then in one word it implies a massive dearth of worth, evidence, and poignancy. It's ingenious in its brief and dismissive/derisive value... in that Shermer clearly feels no need to explain why the point is not useful. One thing that is obvious to me is the EU and Dave in particular have been too honest with less than honest people, and it opens them up to very unfair critique. Note the article Shermer wrote has almost no citations. Oh.

(12)“Conventional psychology was challenged by Gary Schwartz of the University of Arizona, who, in keeping with the electrical themes of the day, explained that the brain is like a television set and consciousness is like the signals coming into the brain. You need a brain to be conscious, but consciousness exists elsewhere. But TV studios generate and broadcast signals.(13) Where, I inquired, is the consciousness equivalent to such production facilities? No answer.”

12. Is this a smear on psychology or televisions, or a hypothesis? It isn't clear. One supposes one has to agree.
13. Non-sequitur. If the proposal of a hypothesis is there, and the fundamental science is not yet done or perhaps concluded, or even classified, why would one expect a “production facility”? If there are any, they'd be controlled by the CIA or HAARP, etc. Is he making the psychologist out to be a conspiracy *theorist* or does he want to talk about conspiracy facts? Shermer is vague, and that tells us something about his agenda. He doesn't want to discuss it further, because for him it's cuckoo. Except, actually it isn't¹², and NSA-funded remote-viewing¹³ studies are in the literature¹⁴, and much more than that.¹⁵ Shermer is misleading his cognitively-biased audience. It's shameful, just shameful, unethical and immoral behavior!

*(14) “A self-taught mathematician named Stephen Crothers¹⁶ riffled through dozens of PowerPoint slides chockablock full of equations related to Einstein's general theory of relativity, (15) which he characterized as “numerology.” Einstein's errors, Crothers proclaimed, led to the mistaken belief in black holes and the big bang. (16) I **understood none of what he was saying**, (17) but I am confident he's wrong by the fact that for a*

¹² <https://www.everythingselectric.com/electric-universe-debunked/>

¹³ <https://irp.fas.org/program/collect/stargate.htm>

¹⁴ <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu/NSAEBB/NSAEBB534-DIA-Declassified-Sourcebook/documents/DIA-21.pdf>

¹⁵ See Page 31

¹⁶ <http://www.sjcrothers.plasmaresources.com/Shermer.html>

century thousands of physicists have challenged Einstein, and (18) still he stands as Time's Person of the Century."

14. This attack is one that really rankles the author. The author is not self-taught, but went to University. The fact is that Universities only teach one thing: Standard Model. That's a glaring omission of the fact that the IEEE has supported plasma cosmology and Electric Universe ideas since well before the Big Bang was a thing.
15. Well, in essence Einstein was a numerologist. Not sure if this is meant as a smear or not? The fact remains that if Einstein is "wrong" (and the author assures you, he is wrong), not about relativity but about space-time, then this is a very critical problem for the SM.
16. Then you are not qualified to criticize him. One who would understand, is Professor Hooft, which this author has already shown to be a crankpot Nobel Prize winner who thinks the Earth is "two-dimensional".¹⁷ So understanding Einstein apparently requires joining a cult of the insane where you do not talk about real particles but instead Zero Particles and Tachyons, which do not exist.¹⁸
17. Einstein published several alterations and corrections, and the point is still that 1st Order Differential Invariants in Unimodular Coordinates were disproven in 1901. So his work never could be justified. At any rate, you cannot divide by zero.
18. Uh oh, a fame **and** authority fallacy. The author now declares victory over Michael Shermer, because this is a no-no in scientific review.

"The EU folks I met were unfailingly polite, unquestionably smart and steadfastly unwavering in their belief that they (19) have made one of the most important discoveries in the history of science. Have they? (20) Probably not. The problem was articulated in a comment Thornhill made when I asked for their peer-reviewed papers: "In an interdisciplinary science like the Electric Universe, you could say we have no peers, (21) so peer review is not available." Without peer review or the requisite training in each discipline, (22) how are we to know the difference between mainstream and alternative theories, of which there are many?"

19. They are very polite people, but one would think they'd prefer respect done to their work, which Shermer obviously had not read. He was too busy sucking up to his echo chamber of sycophants and dunking on people that had treated him politely. However, what discoveries have they made? These are the most important ones:
 - a. Electric comets¹⁹

¹⁷

https://www.academia.edu/73271902/Paradigm_Shift_Comparison_EPEMC_vs_The_Rest_Comparing_PEMC_EU_PU_MU_and_SM_BSM

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/65713466/Schnoll_Effect_the_Relativity_Answer

¹⁹ To be honest, asteroids are electric, too, but relative to the sun, they are neutralized. The electrification of comets is probably related to their being as of yet not neutralized post Shamash breakdown. It isn't clear to the author that Thornhill has made this statement, but the author wishes to attribute it to him, at any rate.

- b. Electric stars²⁰
- c. Transformer Earth²¹
- d. PEM Sky basics²²
- e. Electrogeology
- f. A better mechanism to understanding Climate Change²³
- g. The application and general use of plasmaglyphics and plasmascripts²⁴
- h. And more...

20. Probably yes, but admittedly they have troubles with marketing due to the polarizing nature of the name of the group. The author has recently discussed this elsewhere.
21. That's why EPEMC now exists; it's the next generation engineered to make the *world* its peer, and not be above it, looking down on the masses. Your prestige matters little. Only Truth matters. And with that comes data and evidence.
22. Seems like study is pretty important, with or without peer review. It is a bit of a non-sequitur to assume and even presume that peer review journals are needed to discern differences. Granted, it's easier when you have one side propagandizing and even moralizing the issue, as a weapon, in order to maintain its power. Peer Review journals help do that. In a way, Shermer is conceding the author's point preemptively to him making it.

(23) *"In his book The Electric Kool-Aid Acid Test, Tom Wolfe quotes Merry Prankster Ken Kesey: "You're either on the bus or off the bus."(24) **It's not that EUers are wrong; they're** (25) not even on the bus."*

23. At the very end, he finally gives one, potentially out of context, citation.

Figure 1 - Slow clap ([gif](#)); credit: KnowYourMeme

²⁰ Alfvén-Juergens-Scott

²¹ Leybourne

²² Uyen-Peratt-Davidson ; the author's own work is much more visually comprehensive, but definitely chronologically later and owes much to these works.

²³ one that doesn't require killing the world economy and an industry (to help Socialists in their bid for power over our very lives in an ESG score social credit system).

²⁴ Although the author has pioneered a much better set of tools in EPEMC for future analysis.

Even though the quote is once removed. The quote itself is a bit blasé. That isn't the question. The question is **what bus do you want to be on?** The one that has been lying about COVID, and trying to force you into a fascist New World Order, and also trying to force you to harm your children? One that has polluted the world and created a War Economy? Or one that unites different forms of religion and spirituality and in a way that definitely seeks to improve the world's health, lifespan, and harmony; one that promotes oneness with a greater, unified, and real Force? For the author: he is decidedly on the side of the Rebellion.

24. That's good to know. Shermer admits the EU people are right by including this. What he misses is the fact that...
25. The EU people, and the author and EPEMC people, do not want to be on the bus. The bus is going over the cliff on fire.

Figure 2 - This is Fine (gif); credit: IceGif

We want to build a better bus that includes everyone, even ones that disagree, and carries mankind into a SPACER²⁵ and safer future²⁶. Space for the mainstream is about war²⁷ and exploitation²⁸. Or death²⁹ and darkness³⁰. That's not a future, but an anti-MIMS³¹. It is worthless.

²⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers?authuser=0>

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

²⁷

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

²⁸ https://www.academia.edu/67829412/Technology_as_the_0th_War_Domain

²⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ultimate_fate_of_the_universe

³⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-020-02338-w>

³¹ anti -MIMS are means to destroy life and future. See:

https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

The Problem Goes Beyond Shermer's Ilk

This person then, drunk on his power, went on to attack Graham Hancock³². He later regretted this on the Joe Rogan Podcast when he was called out and admitted he needed to do a retraction.³³

Let me be clear: people like Shermer are **not scientists**. They are paid by the mainstream cults to protect their little fragile havens of Standard Model faux science and pseudoscience³⁴ (a priori, non-sequitur, mathemagicks, etc.), to make magazines which serve as the metaphysics equivalent to real journals. But the problem extends well beyond such fake skeptics. Real skeptics provide *questions*, and scientists try to answer those questions. However, haters and imaginationless, asinine peanut gallery salesmen like Shermer do nothing for science, and a great deal against it³⁵. They're the type of people hired by Edison to defend Direct Current and label men like Tesla as dangerous to society³⁶. They slow progress, not help it. Not even a little bit.³⁷ Paid shills and naysayers, is all that they function as, not skeptics.

But the problem is far wider, if you think about it. When one examines the book burnings³⁸ and anti-Velikovskianism³⁹ headed by department chiefs at prestigious Universities (like Harvard⁴⁰), the attacks on Halton Arp⁴¹, the facts of who and what Carl Sagan really was and his role as a government stooge⁴², and look at the evidence that these journals are vacuous cesspools of fake science⁴³ and sensationalism⁴⁴, with little to no oversight⁴⁵, you realize that the problem is systemic.⁴⁶ It is academic⁴⁷ ⁴⁸, governmental⁴⁹, related to military contracting⁵⁰, and of

³² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tFIAFo78xoQ>

³³ He even failed at this, while doing it
https://www.skeptic.com/reading_room/debating-science-lost-civilizations-shermer-experience-on-joe-rogan-961/

³⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer>

³⁵ <http://milesmathis.com/thunder.pdf>

³⁶ People like Shermer and Sagan are the ones hired to smear real scientists, their betters, by mouths that want to silence a certain minority and maintain a position in relative homeostasis. Literally they are the kinds of people that helped Tesla die poor.

³⁷ What positivity, like TED talks, is lost on the negative impact (chilling, as is meant) there is upon young scientific minds.

³⁸ <https://books.google.com/books?id=Xd8UN4Ryn5gC&pg=PA84>

³⁹ https://people.physics.carleton.ca/~watson/Physics/LinR/LinR_2010/Idea_5.5_Velikovsky.pdf

⁴⁰ <https://www.varchive.org/lec/harv.htm>

⁴¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KmotCQCxQEI&t=1s>

⁴² Project A119 <https://nsarchive2.gwu.edu//NSAEFB/NSAEFB479/docs/EBB-Moon02.pdf>

⁴³ <https://retractionwatch.com/2017/07/25/may-sting-another-journal-prank-good-overlook/>

⁴⁴

<https://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-6239071/Academic-journals-caught-massive-hoax-involving-20-FAKE-papers.html>

⁴⁵ <https://www.cbsnews.com/news/computerized-fake-research-papers-get-published/>

⁴⁶

<https://www.newyorker.com/tech/annals-of-technology/paging-dr-fraud-the-fake-publishers-that-are-ruining-science>

⁴⁷

<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2018/aug/10/predatory-publishers-the-journals-who-churn-out-fake-science>

⁴⁸ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4206639/>

⁴⁹ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/how-bad-is-the-governments-science-1523915765>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2991133/>

course enables the Big Pharma⁵¹/Big Chemical⁵² and energy/oil industries⁵³ to continue in their obviously bad directions, unabated. It's like a psyop; one which we call "controlled opposition."⁵⁴

It is so bad that the journal industry has been caught publishing fake science and other issues such as forged papers⁵⁵, AI-written papers⁵⁶, etc. The more "woke" it is, too, making ridiculous claims⁵⁷ (behaving in this way how quantum mechanics did in its inception⁵⁸), the more it is promulgated and encouraged. Simultaneous to this is a bit of Pew Research showing that "the Left" has had its brains scattered out the side⁵⁹, probably as the right hemisphere of the brain needs boundaries and lines set by the left hemisphere. But, without direct studies with fMRI, we won't know for sure. The research was in 2017, and this has gone further south both politically, and in Academia, with more and more fake research showing up, and greater amounts of cosmological pseudoscience not couched (as we do in EPEMC) as philosophy or opinion, or hypothesis, but as already proven fact. Well, it isn't fact. It is just drivel: negative mass⁶⁰, dark photons⁶¹, etc. Will people like Shermer call this out? Not likely. Instead he will attack his betters who have spent decades in study and contemplation, relying upon evidence⁶².

The entire peer review cult is this way. They want alt-streamers like Hancock and Schoch and Carlson to bow the knee, but then will berate them anyway⁶³. It's mind control stuff, like MK-ULTRA⁶⁴. But this type of gaslighting⁶⁵ has become so common in our society that even math⁶⁶, logic⁶⁷, and rationalism⁶⁸ are 'under attack' *within* the Scientific community at large! Which tells the author something specific: it isn't about truth for the mainstream anymore, but prestige, position, and money. Access is the main motivation, and that means to the press and grant money. AKA access to government power. Ie: fascism.

How the Mainstream Obfuscates Real Science - Lies by Omission

The biggest proof of this is the way that the mainstream lies by omission. They will, to their credit, put out a simple article about a disclusion, or debunking of previous thought. If they didn't, we'd never hear about it. In fact, probably it happens more than we know. Nevertheless,

⁵¹ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1420798/>

⁵² <https://www.dcatvci.org/features/the-merger-of-dow-chemical-and-dupont-a-pharma-industry-view/>

⁵³ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/exxon-knew-about-climate-change-almost-40-years-ago/>

⁵⁴ <https://definedictionarymeaning.com/topic/91446/controlled-opposition/1>

⁵⁵

<https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/morning-mix/wp/2015/08/18/outbreak-of-fake-peer-reviews-widens-as-major-publisher-retracts-64-scientific-papers/>

⁵⁶ <https://news.mit.edu/2019/can-science-writing-be-automated-ai-0418>

⁵⁷ <https://www.nytimes.com/2018/10/04/arts/academic-journals-hoax.html>

⁵⁸ "We are all agreed that your theory is crazy. The question which divides us is whether it is crazy enough to have a chance of being correct. My own feeling is that it is not crazy enough." ~Niels Bohr

⁵⁹ See p.64, Figure 35

⁶⁰ https://www.academia.edu/37972998/Pseudoscience_Cannot_Be_Dark_Matter

⁶¹ https://www.academia.edu/63382042/ Something_from_Nothing

⁶² Rock, rune, earthwork, maths/ratios, logic, and laboratory (plasma) evidence.

⁶³ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/no-there-wasnt-an-advanced-civilization-12-000-years-ago/>

⁶⁴ See p.31, Figure 18

⁶⁵ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/gaslighting>

⁶⁶ <https://www.nationalreview.com/2021/09/the-folly-of-woke-math/>

⁶⁷ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/good-western-logic-as-merely-white-privilege-oppression-11604865500>

⁶⁸ <https://rowman.com/ISBN/9780742542815/White-Logic-White-Methods-Racism-and-Methodology>

a simple one article story is not the same as the nonstop barrage of media marketing done when something goes, or appears to go, their way. The author is now going to juxtapose two such situations: M87 as a “photographed black hole” and gravity waves “being proven/discovered” with new science that refutes black hole theory (again), and also proof that energy and matter (mass-energy) are not being studied or understood correctly, as the new data on fusion suggests.

This juxtaposition of these is not explainable in SM or Big Bang Cosmology, without mental gymnastics, but is completely explainable in EU/PU or EPEMC cosmologies. Easily.

The worst form of lie, in this author’s opinion, is to lie by omission. That’s why it is good, even when being critical of a person, to state what is their due. “To your credit” is an easy line to memorize. It also shows that you appreciate their work.

To the mainstream’s credit: they build the equipment, and excepting LIGO and the Cosmic Background Radiation measurements⁶⁹ inside the Earth’s atmosphere^{70,71} they’ve done a generally good job of measuring and reporting the data. However, the fact that there still is data manipulation, or ignoring of data, is a serious problem in the mainstream. But the “lab” of Mother Nature cannot be assailed by such nonsense. No more than anti-biological ‘studies’ overthrow the facts of the Universe.⁷²

Therefore, we have to consider the next proposition: that there are purposeful, misleading lies, or double-speak⁷³ (more commonly), which is designed to mislead the public and obfuscate scientific progress⁷⁴. Why?⁷⁵ All this author can think of is to hide the progress of military and biomedical research (and technocratic advantage) from the [mostly bovine⁷⁶, pacified] public/consumers. In other words: money.

This isn’t just to hide stealth bombers⁷⁷ (and their potential electric drives) and the like. It is to give literal propaganda, marketing, and technological advantage (Shi⁷⁸) of the elite over the populace. If that elite is friends with elite pseudoscientists who speak in drivel about completely made up nonsense⁷⁹ (what the author calls GNOMES⁸⁰), the remaining fact is just the same as the Third Reich’s propaganda machine⁸¹. A populace turned upon itself. Except that the People are the government in the West.

⁶⁹ COBE <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=edpn14aMxnY>

⁷⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WOoxNeL6lFw>

⁷¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cqM6lZOvZcs>

⁷² XX and XY (and by extension XYY), that’s it. That’s all there is.

⁷³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/doublespeak>

⁷⁴ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5686505/>

⁷⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1420798/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2018/02/180215110041.htm>

⁷⁷

<https://blackwells.co.uk/bookshop/product/Electrogravitics-Systems-by-Thomas-Valone/9780964107007>

⁷⁸ https://www.academia.edu/51643169/MIMS_2_6_2_Strategy_and_Dualism

⁷⁹ https://www.academia.edu/65713466/Schnoll_Effect_the_Relativity_Answer

⁸⁰ https://www.academia.edu/49497635/Converting_GNOME_CDM_Mass_Ratios_joke_paper

⁸¹

<https://slate.com/news-and-politics/2017/03/how-nazi-propaganda-encouraged-the-masses-to-co-produce-a-false-reality.html>

Table 1 - Comparing Claims and Facts in the Standard Model

<p style="text-align: center;">M87</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Claimed to be a black hole ● Claimed to be photographed⁸² ● Is asymmetric⁸³ ● No evidence of accretion⁸⁴ ● Strong evidence of electromagnetic behavior⁸⁵ ● Data arranged a priori to obtain image ● Rotations as predicted in plasmoid physics ● Is massaged data⁸⁶ 	<p style="text-align: center;">Vampire Star HR6819</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Claimed to be a black hole ● Claimed to be close to the Sun in Milky Way⁸⁷ ● Claimed to be extremely powerful ● Signal has disappeared ● Analysis shows it was never a physical object in that location⁸⁸ ● Might be two stars orbiting tightly ● Lost too much mass to be a “black hole”
<p style="text-align: center;">Gravity Waves/LIGO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Claimed to be postulated by Einstein⁸⁹ ● Claimed to be found by LIGO⁹⁰ ● Claimed to have confirmation⁹¹ ● Claimed to cross “branes” and other hyperdimensionality⁹² ● Claimed to perhaps move faster than light⁹³ ● Does not account for all noise in signals ● Is massaged data⁹⁴ ● Has not been found decisively 	<p style="text-align: center;">Fusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Claimed to be caused by gravity pressures inside star cores ● Claims to create energy ● Claims to be doable with lasers (whose particles hit at high pressure) ● Requires plasma⁹⁵, magnetism⁹⁶, radio waves⁹⁷, etc. to control ● Happens even at low energies⁹⁸ ● Is now proven to take place in Z-pinches⁹⁹

⁸² <https://www.space.com/first-black-hole-photo-by-event-horizon-telescope.html>

⁸³ <https://spectrum.ieee.org/the-inside-story-of-the-first-picture-of-a-black-hole>

⁸⁴ Literally the asymmetry reveals the opposite, especially with the rotation mapped.

⁸⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J4NffTr_GMk

⁸⁶ <https://eventhorizontelescope.org/blog/astromers-image-magnetic-fields-edge-m87s-black-hole>

⁸⁷ < 1,000 light years

⁸⁸ <https://www.inverse.com/science/the-closest-black-hole-to-earth-was-never-really-there>

⁸⁹ It was actually H. Poincare

⁹⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ev10ywLFq6E>

⁹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=45BGbnJykPo>

⁹² <http://home.iitk.ac.in/~osegu/StringTheory.pdf>

⁹³ <https://usm.maine.edu/planet/do-gravity-waves-travel-light-speed>

⁹⁴

<https://www.newscientist.com/article/mg24032022-600-exclusive-grave-doubts-over-ligos-discovery-of-gravitational-waves/>

⁹⁵ <https://www.pppl.gov/about/about-plasmas-and-fusion>

⁹⁶ <https://news.mit.edu/2021/MIT-CFS-major-advance-toward-fusion-energy-0908>

⁹⁷ <https://www.popularmechanics.com/science/a32389687/radio-waves-stabilize-fusion-reactions/>

⁹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PbDBSsuNdyc>

⁹⁹ <https://phys.org/news/2022-03-scientists-thermonuclear-fusion-sheared-flow-z-pinch.html>

So therefore, this is a *treasonous* action¹⁰⁰, or at least highly treacherous. The scientific community is, more than you realize, quite literally in bed with government¹⁰¹ and media propagandists¹⁰², and many academics are either spies, saboteurs, corporate espionage experts¹⁰³, or just generally purveyors of misinformation & disinformation¹⁰⁴. This is a conspiracy fact, and the list of these kinds of events and historical situations are documented in many places and in great books with lots of citations (see Table 3). Therefore, enjoy the next section which lays out actual facial/screenshot documentation about the “what’s going on”, from topics ranging from COVID and military to population control, climate science, space drives, etc. These documents are quite publicly available. The “lie” is simply that the mainstream doesn’t want you to know about them. That’s the problem with echo chambers¹⁰⁵. If you don’t step outside of your safe space¹⁰⁶, you won’t hear this kind of information.

Figure 3 - Safe Space (gif); credit: South Park

¹⁰⁰ In that the People are the government, and the actions of leading a government to harm the People is itself treason. American patriotism is anti-nationalist.

¹⁰¹

<https://delval.edu/news/science-or-government-propaganda-freedoms-laboratory-author-talk-with-audra-wole>

¹⁰²

<https://www.nbcnews.com/tech/tech-news/more-governments-ever-are-using-social-media-push-propaganda-report-n1076301>

¹⁰³ <https://usnwc.libguides.com/c.php?g=661096&p=5275270> & <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1057/9780230373174>

¹⁰⁴ <https://guides.lib.uw.edu/c.php?g=345925&p=7772376>

¹⁰⁵ <https://edu.gcfglobal.org/en/digital-media-literacy/what-is-an-echo-chamber/1/>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/safe%20space>

Table 2 - List of Reputable Books to Study

<i>PEM cosmology</i>	<i>Comparative Mythology</i>	<i>Conspiracy Facts</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ “Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond” ❖ “The Electric Sun” ❖ “The Physics of the Plasma Universe” ❖ “Introduction to Plasma Physics” ❖ “Plasma Physics” ❖ “The Electric Universe” ❖ “The Big Bang Never Happened” ❖ “The Nature of the Atom” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ★ “Worlds in Collision” etc. ★ “Flare God” (series) ★ “The Saturn Theory” ★ “Thunderbolts of the Gods” ★ “Starf*cker” ★ “Gobekli Tepe: Genesis of the Gods” ★ “The Holy Kingdom” ★ “Arthur: First King of the Brits” ★ “The King Arthur Conspiracy” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ “Space Force: Our Star Trek Future” ❖ “Secrets from the Black Vault” ❖ “Secret Empires” ❖ “Hundred Year Marathon” ❖ “Stealth War” ❖ “To Loot a Burning House” ❖ “Deceiving the Sky” ❖ “A Republic Under Assault”
<i>War & Strategy</i>	<i>Economics & Business</i>	<i>Etc.</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ★ “The Seven Military Classics” ★ “The 36 Stratagems” ★ “48 Laws of Power” ★ “The Art of Chess” ★ “Unrestricted Warfare” ★ “Thick Black Theory” ★ “Sun Bin: the Art of Warfare” ★ “Thunder in the Sky” ★ “Unorthodox Strategies: 100 Lessons in the Art of War” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ “The New Case for Gold” ❖ “GRUNCH of Giants” ❖ “How to Be a Millionaire” ❖ “Money: Master the Game” ❖ “Modern Money Mechanics” ❖ “The Midas Touch” ❖ “The Rockefeller Habits” ❖ “Your First 100 Million” ❖ “Tough-Minded Management” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ★ “Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt” ★ “Competing on Analytics” ★ “Tao of Physics” ★ “The Stone Monkey” ★ “The Cycle of Cosmic Catastrophes” ★ “When the Earth Nearly Died” ★ “Giza Power Plant” ★ “The Great Reset” ★ “Mankind in Amnesia” ★ “The I Ching”

Declassified Facts and Documents

The following are images from Salla’s and Greenwald Jr.’s books, used here as a fair use of education. Please buy the books. My photographs will not do it justice, and if you try to do the same FOIA for these projects, you’ll be waiting years, and “beating a dead horse.”

I’ll produce, nevertheless, a list of the declassified projects for you to research, after the images.

- ❖ Remember, the purpose of this is to explain an underworld of scientific and technological “innovation” (meaning secret testing which was harmful to people and the environment) that got going after World War II, and has included (yes), COVID-19.

Below: Figure 4 - This document establishes one of the linchpins for the discussion of secret space programs, proving that certain individuals worked for the government. Few people can corroborate their sources, and Salla has.

NAME (LAST, FIRST, MIDDLE INITIAL) Fouche, Edgar A		SSAN FR4 [REDACTED]	AUG 20 1979 ACTIVE DUTY GRADE TSGT
(CHECK APPROPRIATE BLOCK AND COMPLETE AS APPLICABLE)			
<input type="checkbox"/> SUPPLEMENTAL SHEET TO RATING FORM WHICH COVERS THE FOLLOWING PERIOD OF REPORT		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> LETTER OF EVALUATION COVERING THE FOLLOWING PERIOD OF OBSERVATION	
FROM	THRU	FROM	THRU
		10 June 79	14 AUG 79
<p>Precede comments by appropriate data, i.e. section continuation, indorsement continuation, additional indorsement, additional reviewer comments, etc.</p> <p>FACTS AND SPECIFIC ACHIEVEMENTS: TSgt Fouche is an outstanding NCO and technician. His exceptional performance of all duties, even under adverse conditions, indicates a dedicated interest in his work, and a high degree of professionalism. His wide-ranging knowledge and diverse expertise in diagnostics, and mechanical engineering, coupled with his training in advanced electronics, has helped solve critical mission support problems consistently. His awareness of the big picture for future avionics development and maintenance is an attribute that makes him a valuable asset to TAC. TSgt Fouche is considered one of TACs best R&D team builders in areas of ECM, ATS, and cryptological support. He has proven himself recently in the implementation of the TEWS-TITE bed-down, which was lauded by TAC Hq LGM. STRENGTHS: TSgt Fouche displays excellent capabilities when given greater responsibilities, which was demonstrated in his MAJCOM involvement in cryptological asset training and provisioning. He has high endorsements from his chain of command and is considered an excellent candidate for a command level position. OTHER COMMENTS: This out of cycle report is generated because TSgt Fouche was assigned TDY to the AFFTC-DET 3, Nellis AF Range from 1 June 79 to 14 August 79. His duties and responsibilities for this period have been verified via a separate report. RECOMMENDATION: Promote at the earliest opportunity.</p>			
NAME OF EVALUATOR, GRADE, ORGANIZATION, AND LOCATION [REDACTED] Brewer, MSgt, USAF 57 CRS, Nellis AFB Nevada		DUTY TITLE NCOIC F-15 AIS SSAN (INCLUDE SUFFIX) FR465-[REDACTED]	DATE 24 Aug 79 SIGNATURE [REDACTED] Brewer
AF FORM 77b PREVIOUS EDITION WILL BE USED.		U.S. GOVERNMENT PRINTING OFFICE: 1976-211-391/1105	
		SUPPLEMENTAL SHEET TO AF FORM 707, 909, 910, 911 AND 475	

Figure 5 - Did the United States have a secret moon base? Was it destroyed? What's the real reason we have not gone back to the moon?; credit: Salla

Below: Figure 6- The Vastness of conspiracy facts includes trusted public companies. Not only Dow etc., but even General Mills. What they tested on people will shock you; credit: Greenwald

Figure 1.2. The cover page for the eighth quarterly progress report, submitted by General Mills, in contract DA-18-064-CML-2745. Credit: US Government

*Interim Report
of the
Advisory Committee
on
Human
Radiation
Experiments*

October 21, 1994

DISCLAIMER

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MASTER

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Figure 3.1. In 1994, President Bill Clinton sanctioned the Advisory Committee on Human Radiation Experiments, which released their report the same year. This is a cover page from one of the original, interim reports by the committee. *Credit: US Government*

Figure 7 & 8 (below) - Regarding MK-ULTRA... What was the (now proven monstrous) Clintons' interests? We may never know; credit: Greenwald

Date 6 JULY 1977

DRAFT
1 May 1953

MEMORANDUM FOR THE RECORD

SUBJECT: Project MKULTRA, Subproject 2

1. Subproject 2 is being set up to provide a secure and efficient means to exploit [redacted] in regard to the MKULTRA program. — C

C — 2. [redacted] is a practicing psychiatrist in [redacted] and a faculty member of the [redacted]. His past positions have included Chief Neuropsychiatrist at [redacted] Chief of the Psychiatric Section at [redacted] and OSS experience during World War II. He has been of value in the general MKULTRA field as an overall advisor and consultant, he has been of value in contacting individuals in the [redacted] area and in setting up projects there, and he has done work himself which has contributed to the MKULTRA field. His professional activities and known connections with the [redacted] — B

3. Subproject 2 would include:

a. Miscellaneous research and testing services in the general field of MKULTRA.

b. Services as a contact and cut-out for projects in the MKULTRA field, primarily those located in the [redacted] areas. — C

c. Monitoring of selected projects in the MKULTRA field, when located in the central [redacted] area. — C

d. Services as a general consultant and advisor in the MKULTRA field.

4. The total cost of this project is not to exceed \$4,650.00 for a period of one year.

C — 5. [redacted] is cleared through TOP SECRET on a contact basis.

[redacted signature block]
date 6 JUL 1977

[redacted signature block]
Chemical Division/TSS

APPROVED:

Figure 3.3. Undated letter from the Director of the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) to Senator Daniel K. Inouye regarding the lost MKULTRA files that were recently discovered. Credit: Central Intelligence Agency (CIA)

Figure 9 - So the CIA really is up to no good? It's not a conspiracy theory, it's a fact; credit: Greenwald

Figure 4.3. The cover page for the Fearless Johnny test during Project SHAD. Credit: Department of Defense (DOD)

there were eighteen total toxicological and biological agents utilized, that came in contact in some way, with the 5,800 military personnel that took part over the course of approximately eleven years. The complete list includes the following:

1. *Bacillus globigii* (BG)
2. Betapropiolactone (beta-propiolactone; BPL)
3. Bis Hydrogen Phosphite (BHP)
4. Calcofluor
5. *Coxiella burnetii* (CB; Q fever)
6. Diethyl phthalate (DEP or D)
7. *Escherichia coli* [*E. coli*]
8. Methyl Acetoacetate (MAA)
9. Phosphorus-32 [³²P]
10. Sarin
11. *Serratia marcescens* (SM)
12. Staphylococcal Enterotoxin Type B (SEB)

Figure 10 & 11 (below) - Project SHAD, human testing on 5,800 soldiers, list of pathogens; credit: Greenwald

13. Sulfur Dioxide (SO₂)
14. Trioctyl Phosphate (TEHP or TOF)
15. *Pasteurella tularensis* (*Francisella tularensis*)
16. Uranine
17. VX Nerve Agent (VX)
18. Zinc Cadmium Sulfide (ZnCdS)

Each one of the eighteen on this list deserves a lengthy explanation to detail the breakdown, composition, effects, and dangers that some of them pose. I chose only a couple to highlight, in order to display how dangerous these tests really were, and how the various phases of the program played out.

The outrage by the public that prompted the 2002 congressional hearing was partially sparked by the inclusion of a few of these compounds and biological agents on this list. A year after the public was made aware of Projects 112 and SHAD, CBS News and the Associated Press continued their reporting, and on July 1, 2003, published an article that outlined continued secrecy and cover-up of this issue. They stated:

The Pentagon is continuing to withhold documents on Cold War chemical and biological weapons tests that used unsuspecting sailors as "human samplers" after telling Congress it had released all medically relevant information.

The Vietnam Veterans of America is suing Pentagon officials on behalf of the sailors, demanding the release of all of the test documents so the National Academ[y] of Science can fully analyze the potential health effects.

Douglas Rosinski, an attorney working with the veterans group on behalf of the soldiers, said the effects of the chemicals on the sailors has not been studied. The levels of exposure that the documents might detail is a crucial piece of the puzzle, he said.

There was, at the time this CBS News article was published, an ongoing study initiated by the US government. However, the results were not finished, as it was part of a three-year, three-million-dollar contract with the Institute of Medicine, Medical Follow-up Agency of the National Academy of Sciences awarded on September 30, 2002. The aim was to evaluate the long-term health issues, if any, from the Project SHAD experiments. The results of this study were published in 2007 and totaled nearly one hundred

3)

NOT APPROVED FOR
RELEASE 1 JULY 2015
HANDLE VIA BYEMAN SYSTEM ONLY
~~SECRET/DORIAN~~

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17460 14

SPACEBORNE COMMAND POST CHARACTERISTICS

	12 MAN STATION	40 MAN STATION
CAPABILITY	LIKE EC 135 AIRBORNE CMD POST	LIKE CSA AIRBORNE CMD POST
WEIGHT	165000 LB	470,000 LB
VOLUME	13,400 FT ³	37,200 FT ³
POWER	10 KW (SOLAR ARRAYS)	26 KW (SOLAR OR [REDACTED])
CONFIGURATION	CYLINDER	3 MATED CYLINDERS
RESUPPLY (INCLUDING PERSONNEL TRANSFER VEHICLES)	70,000 LB/2MO.	230,000 LB/E MO
MANEUVERABILITY	1000 FT/SEC	1000 FT/SEC
FUNCTIONS		
• SELF DEFENSE	YES	YES
• WIDE BAND DATA PROCESSING	NO	YES
• STATUS MONITORING	YES	YES
• COMMUNICATIONS	YES	YES
• INFORMATION ANALYSIS	LIMITED	YES
• STRATEGIC/TACTICAL DECISION MAKING	LIMITED	YES
• FORCE CONTROL	LIMITED	YES

Figure 24. General Electric proposal for Spaceborne Command Posts.

Figure 12 - Project DORIAN, secret spaceport planning; makes you wonder where a lot of that “missing” Pentagon money went; credit: Salla

Bear in mind these facts:

- ★ The missing money was never audited¹⁰⁷, because the day after Donald Rumsfeld (member of the secret society “Project for a New American Century”¹⁰⁸) announced a tremendous audit of the Pentagon on 9/10/01, September 11th attacks happened.¹⁰⁹
- ★ It so happens that he was also announcing a Space Force¹¹⁰
- ★ The Black Budget of the CIA is officially small, but unofficially is over \$1.1T,¹¹¹ bigger than the Pentagon’s¹¹²... and could not all be spent at Langley. Even on the author’s map there’s only 8 known CIA black sites... but how many are there, really? Many more than eight.

¹⁰⁷

<https://www.npr.org/2021/05/19/997961646/the-pentagon-has-never-passed-an-audit-some-senators-want-to-change-that>

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.duo.uio.no/bitstream/handle/10852/25398/Ferdigxmasteroppgave.pdf>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MfMjdKElqgY>

¹¹⁰ <https://aerospace.csis.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/RumsfeldCommission.pdf>

¹¹¹ https://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/exopolitica/esp_exopolitica_i_1b.htm

¹¹² \$766.6 billion (2020) www.statista.com/statistics/272473/us-military-spending-from-2000-to-2012/

Figure 13 - US Military Empire Map (in progress); credit: author, and sources (multiple, public)
The author knows there are more in the southern hemisphere, and has sent a FOIA to SOUTHCOM/SOCOM
Figure 14(below) - NRO-CIA joint Secret Space Program DORIAN; credit: Salla

Figure 4.1. Operation LAC utilized the C-119 “Flying Boxcar” to disperse zinc cadmium sulfide in massive quantities. *Credit:* Department of Defense (DOD)

Figure 15 - Operation LAC were the original chemtrail programs. Chemtrails are a conspiracy fact, but at this point what is more interesting is that they changed the term to “geoengineering”¹¹³ now that it’s out in the open¹¹⁴, and hold conferences¹¹⁵. These programs are not voted for. The only thing that was kept it in the dark, prior to 2010 when all the hubbub brought it public on the web¹¹⁶, was a fear the American and European people might actually do something about it. Now it is being sold as necessary to save the planet from “man-made” Climate Change¹¹⁷...;credit: Greenwald

¹¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Climate_engineering

¹¹⁴ China publicly announced its plans to spray nickel in 2018
<https://chinadialogue.net/en/climate/how-to-supervise-geoengineering/>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.grc.org/climate-engineering-conference/2022/>

¹¹⁶ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43868685>

¹¹⁷ <https://www.grc.org/climate-engineering-conference/2022/>

<https://www.usatoday.com> > factcheck > 2022/02/25 > f... ⋮

Fact check: Oregon weather broadcast isn't proof of chemtrails ...

Claim: A weatherman admitted the military is 'spraying chemtrails'

Claimed by: Social media users

Fact check by **USA Today: False** **"Don't believe your lying eyes"**

[Feedback](#)

Figure 16 - Doing citations, found this IFCN gem. It isn't a conspiracy "theory", chemtrailing is a conspiracy **fact**, as you can see above and below. The author has met people in the conspiracy. Credit: Google/author (search terms: "chemtrail conspiracy 2010"), note the date... this year!

Figure 17 - actual "chemtrail", photo by the US Air Force, Operation Ranch Hand; credit: Greenewald

Figure 18 - China catching up to the US in Space and Military Spending; credit: Salla

Projects Covered in the Salla and Greenwald ([The Black Vault](#)) Books:

[CHURCHY](#)

[SKYHOOK](#)

[MOGUL](#) (1963 Report)

[GENETRIX](#)

[Contract DA-18-064-CML-2745](#)

[CHATTER](#)

[MKULTRA](#) //Kinsey?

→ [Part 1](#)

→ [Part 2](#)

→ [Part 3](#)

→ [Part 4](#)

[BLUEBIRD](#)

[ARTICHOKE](#)

[DEW/II](#)

[LAC](#) (Project 112)

[SHAD](#) (Hearing)

[AUTUMN GOLD](#)

[FEARLESS JOHNNY](#) ([NIGHT TRAIN](#))

[RANCH HAND](#) (study on Use)

- [Agent White](#)
- [Agent Blue](#)
- [Agent Green](#)
- [Agent Pink](#)
- [Agent Orange/II](#) ([Dioxin Report](#))

[PAPERCLIP](#)

["1983 War Scare in US-Soviet Relations"](#)

[ABLE ARCHER](#) // 83 (CIA)

[RYAN](#) (CIA)

[Holystone Program](#)

["Command History" \(1986\)](#) // [Volume 2](#)

[OSCAR II](#) (Oscar-8)

[HORIZON](#)

★ [Vol1](#) ["Summary and Supporting Considerations"](#)

★ [Vol2](#) ["Technical Considerations & Plans"](#)

[A119](#) ([Capability of Nukes in space](#))

[E-1 "A Study of Lunar Research Flights"](#)

[Mission LCROSS](#)

[CORONA](#) (CIA)

[SENTRY Program](#)

[KEYHOLE/ DISCOVERER](#)

[HEXAGON Program](#)

[DORIAN](#)

[Manned Orbiting Laboratory \(MOL\)](#)

[DYNOSOAR \(X-20\)](#)

[CRYSTAL / Misty](#)

[HIGH DIVE](#)

["The Roswell Report" \(1994 USAF Report\)](#)

➤ [vol. 1 \(1995\)](#)

➤ [vol. 2 \(1997\)](#)

[USAF "fact sheet" on UFOs](#)

[BLUE BOOK](#)

["1976 Iran Incident"](#)

[OXCART \(SR-71\)](#) (CIA)

[AATIP](#) (UFOs - 2021)

[SCANATE](#)

[Contract 77F 104420](#)

[GRILL FLAME](#) (CIA)

[SUN STREAK](#)

[Stargate Collection/Program](#)

[PEGASUS](#)¹¹⁸

["Final Report on Organizational and Management Structure for the National Security Space Components of the Department of Defense"](#)

[SPD-4 Report](#)

[LUSTY & S-4 Program @ Area 51](#)

[Majestic-12 Group \(PDF\)](#)

[Aurora Program](#)

[CLASSIC WIZARD](#) (Navy)

["The Black Budget Report" \(of the CIA\)](#)

["2001 Space Commission Report"](#)

["1967 Outer Space Treaty" \(UN\)](#)

[Artemis Program](#)

[HIGH JUMP](#)

["The Dark Fleet"?](#)¹¹⁹

¹¹⁸ At the exact moment I typed this, Perseus was catching Pegasus in the 1981 movie, "Clash of the Titans"

¹¹⁹ The existence of which this author can neither confirm, nor deny.

Modern Conspiracy Fact in Motion: Who Invented mRNA vaccination?

As evidence emerges just how bad the COVID vaccination is^{120 121} - if one can call it that since they changed the definition behind closed doors¹²², to protect the companies from Operation: WARP SPEED¹²³ - and how many side effects it has¹²⁴, more disturbing facts are also emerging. Namely, that *both* the vaccine and the pathogen were manufactured primarily by Moderna¹²⁵ (perhaps explaining why their vaccine is the worst at side effects). It seems almost impossible, based upon a special sequence of codes¹²⁶, that the genome is natural; and indeed, clinically the effects are obviously not¹²⁷. Setting aside the potential connections to the Saturn-Jupiter reconnection, and the Comet Atlas “coincidence” which enabled such a priori accurate reporting as PEAKS and “DOUBLE EVENTS” (which were actually announced a week before showing up in WHO daily data...¹²⁸) the real issue is: does the Nobel winner’s assertions¹²⁹ (who died

¹²⁰ <https://coloradosun.com/2022/01/31/covid-vaccine-failure-antibodies-research/>

¹²¹ <https://willemvincken.wordpress.com/2021/09/30/covid-19-vaccine-experiment-is-a-massive-failure/>

¹²²

<https://newsnationusa.com/news/usanews/dallas/yes-the-cdc-changed-its-definition-of-vaccine-to-be-more-transparent/>

¹²³ <https://www.niaid.nih.gov/grants-contracts/what-operation-warp-speed>

¹²⁴ 1,291 for Pfizer (based on clinical data)

<https://childrenshealthdefense.org/wp-content/uploads/pfizer-doc-5.3.6-postmarketing-experience.pdf#page=30>

¹²⁵ <https://dailyexpose.uk/2022/03/14/documents-published-confirming-moderna-created-covid/>

¹²⁶ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-Az_CmkACpAAP62a_ARpFk8UOtuxpIBU/view?usp=sharing

¹²⁷ The author started seeing SARS like effects clinically in 2015 or 2016; but assumed them to be Bird Flu. However, now after 2020, it is quite obvious the attacks at K22, SI17, RN21 (thymus gland), etc. are part of a plan to weaken the immune system every cold or dry season, and make a person more susceptible to influenza, etc.

¹²⁸

https://www.academia.edu/43190878/OPINION_On_Gurus_Electric_Universe_Predictions_Bio_electrics_Cometes_5G_and_Futurism

¹²⁹

<https://www.soulask.com/luc-montagnier-they-are-not-vaccines-they-are-poisons-speech-to-the-luxembourg-parliament/>

Luc Montagnier said in his speech:

“These vaccines are poisons. They are not real vaccines. The mRNA allows its message to be transcribed throughout the body, uncontrollably. No one can say for each of us where these messages will go. This is therefore a terrible unknown. And in fact we are now learning that this is a work published over a year ago that these mRNAs contain an area that we can call prion, which is an area capable of introducing protein modifications in an unpredictable way. As a doctor I knew 21 people who received 2 doses of Pfizer vaccine, there is another person who received Moderna. The 21 died of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease caused by prions. The 3 vaccines Pfizer, AstraZeneca, Moderna contain a sequence identified by Information Technology as transformation into a prion. There is therefore a known risk to human health.”

“coincidentally” a week after giving interview about the vaccine creating prions¹³⁰) indicate a more serious problem (or indeed conspiracy) behind mRNA work itself?

It doesn’t take long after wading into the plannedemic known as LOCKSTEP¹³¹/EVENT-201¹³² to see issues emerge. The companies who patent and own the pathogen set of coronaviruses, and license them secretly¹³³ to manufacturers (with impunity¹³⁴), and have the government change the terms of death, infection, and side-effect reporting, are **not** the inventors. The

inventor is not dead, he is Dr. Robert Malone, and he has nine patents from his research in the late 1980s on mRNA disease and vaccination.

BNT162b2
5.3.6 Cumulative Analysis of Post-authorization Adverse Event Reports

Figure 1. Total Number of BNT162b2 AEs by System Organ Classes and Event Seriousness

Figure 19 - Adverse Events in FDA approved vaccine trials; unusually high for approved drugs
Credit: CDC/FDA

Table 2 shows the most commonly (≥2%) reported MedDRA (v. 23.1) PTs in the overall dataset (through 28 February 2021).

¹³⁰ “Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease is called prion disease. What are prions anyway?

Prions were discovered relatively recently, they were most studied in the USA, back in England and here in France. A prion is a specific type of protein that can attack and destroy healthy cells, so that they can no longer recover.

Can we say that prions are a serious threat to humanity?

– Unfortunately, we don’t know much about them. At the moment, it can only be argued that prion diseases are fatal and incurable. In the early 1980s, there was a monstrous scandal in France when more than 120 children died of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease. And they got sick because they were vaccinated containing an extract of the human pituitary gland. The material for vaccination was taken from old people who died in nursing homes, but they themselves did not have Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease, but had either Alzheimer’s disease or Parkinson’s disease. Thus, between all these diseases there was something in common, which was not suspected at that time, and something like infection occurred at the molecular level...”

¹³¹ <https://www.rockefellerfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/Annual-Report-2010-1.pdf>

¹³² <https://www.centerforhealthsecurity.org/event201/videos.html>

¹³³ <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/09/17/health/covid-moderna-vaccine.html>

¹³⁴ <https://blog.petrieflom.law.harvard.edu/2021/05/05/covid-vaccine-patent-waiver/>

Below are the listed patents of Dr. Robert Malone¹³⁵

“Robert W. Malone has filed for patents to protect the following inventions. This listing includes patent applications that are pending as well as patents that have already been granted by the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO).”

- **Compounds and methods for enhancing delivery of free polynucleotide**

Publication number: 20040009947

Abstract: The discovery of simple, nontoxic, and pharmaceutically defined methods for genetic modification of cells and tissues would enable development of a variety of molecular medicines. “Free”, ‘direct’, or ‘naked’ polynucleotide administration is a simple, apparently safe, and pharmaceutically defined polynucleotide delivery method. Murine, macaque, and clinical human experiments have demonstrated transfection of various tissues, such as respiratory tissues, after direct application of ‘free’ polynucleotide. However, direct DNA transfection is relatively inefficient in comparison to many transduction systems. The invention herein is directed to transfection enhancing agents which augment the transfection activity of ‘free’ polynucleotide, thereby facilitating the development of simple and safe alternatives to tissue transfection, more particularly respiratory tissue transfection.

Type: Application

Filed: May 27, 2003

Publication date: January 15, 2004

Inventors: Robert W. Malone, Jill G. Malone

- **DNA vaccines for eliciting a mucosal immune response**

Patent number: 6110898

Abstract: The invention consists of a method for inducing production of a mucosal immune response in a host by administration of an antigen-encoding polynucleotide preparation, comprising DNA or RNA encoding an antigenic epitope to a mucosal inductor site in the mucosal tissue of the host. Naked DNA may be administered directly to mucosa, for instance in saline drops, or in a recombinant gene expression vector. Preferably, the recombinant gene expression vectors are not capable of replication or dissemination. The invention also includes the use of live viral vaccines wherein the viruses include immunostimulatory polynucleotides of the invention. According to a preferred method of the invention, a target protein antigen is administered through its expression by a recombinant gene expression vector.

Type: Grant

¹³⁵ <https://patents.justia.com/inventor/robert-w-malone>

Filed: May 23, 1997

Date of Patent: August 29, 2000

Assignee: University of Maryland, Baltimore

Inventors: Robert W. Malone, Jill G. Malone

- **Formulations and methods for generating active cytofectin: polynucleotide transfection complexes**

Patent number: 5925623

Abstract: In the generation of cytofectin:polynucleotide complexes for transfection of cells, formulations, counterions, and reaction conditions for maximizing the transfection include using a cationic amine compound that has the general structure: ##STR1## wherein R.sub.4 and R.sub.5 are a pair of same or different lipoyl moieties selected from a group consisting of an alkyl, alkenyl, alkynyl, alkanoyl, alkenoyl, or alkynoyl groups and for R.sub.1, R.sub.2, and R.sub.3 at least two are hydroxylated, ether containing, or acyloxy containing alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl groups or at least one amine bonded halogen containing moiety selected from a group consisting of a halogenated alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group or a mixture of at least one halogen containing moiety selected from a group consisting of a halogenated alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group and at least one hydroxylated, ether containing, or acyloxy containing alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group, and X.sup.- is an oxyanion or halide counterion.

Type: Grant

Filed: July 15, 1996

Date of Patent: July 20, 1999

Assignee: The Regents of the University of California

Inventors: Michael H. Nantz, Michael J. Bennett, Rajiv P. Balasubramaniam, Alfred M. Aberle, Robert W. Malone

- **Cationic transport reagents**

Patent number: 5892071

Abstract: For use in transporting biologically active species into and through membrane barriers, a symmetrical cationic diamine compound having the general structure ##STR1## wherein m=1-10; R.sub.1 is a hydrogen, an alkyl group, an alkenyl group, a hydroxylated alkyl or alkenyl group, or an ether containing alkyl or alkenyl group; R.sub.2 is an alkyl group, an alkenyl group, or an alkyl or alkenyl containing acyl group; R.sub.3 is a hydrogen, an alkyl group, an alkenyl group, a hydroxylated alkyl or alkenyl group, or an ether containing alkyl or alkenyl group; R.sub.4 is a hydrogen, an alkyl group, an alkenyl group, a hydroxylated alkyl or alkenyl group, or an ether containing alkyl or alkenyl group; and X.sup.- is an anion.

Type: Grant

Filed: September 15, 1995

Date of Patent: April 6, 1999

Assignee: The Regents of The University of California

Inventors: Michael H. Nantz, Michael J. Bennett, Robert W. Malone

- **Polyfunctional cationic cytofectins, formulations and methods for generating active cytofectin: polynucleotide transfection complexes**

Patent number: 5824812

Abstract: Amine containing compounds and their use in the generation of cytofectin:polynucleotide complexes for transfection of cells, formulations, counterions, and reaction conditions for maximizing the transfection include using cationic amine compounds that have the general structure: ##STR1## wherein R.sub.4 and R.sub.5 are a pair of same or different lipoyl moieties selected from a group consisting of an alkyl, alkenyl, alkynyl, alkanoyl, alkenoyl, or alkynoyl groups and for R.sub.1, R.sub.2, and R.sub.3 at least two are hydroxylated, ether containing, or acyloxy containing alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl groups or at least one amine bonded halogen containing moiety selected from a group consisting of a halogenated alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group or a mixture of at least one halogen containing moiety selected from a group consisting of a halogenated alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group and at least one hydroxylated, ether containing, or acyloxy containing alkyl, alkenyl, or alkynyl group, and X.sup.

Type: Grant

Filed: September 17, 1996

Date of Patent: October 20, 1998

Assignee: The Regents of the University of California

Inventors: Michael H. Nantz, Michael J. Bennett, Rajiv P. Balasubramaniam, Alfred M. Aberle, Robert W. Malone

- **Cationic transport reagents**

Patent number: 5744625

Abstract: For use transporting biologically active species into and through membrane barriers, a symmetrical cationic diamine compound having the general structure ##STR1##

Type: Grant

Filed: May 16, 1996

Date of Patent: April 28, 1998

Assignee: The Regents of the University of California

Inventors: Michael H. Nantz, Michael J. Bennett, Robert W. Malone

- **Induction of a protective immune response in a mammal by injecting a DNA sequence**

Patent number: 5589466

Abstract: A method for delivering an isolated polynucleotide such as DNA or RNA, to the interior of a cell in a mammal comprising the injection of an isolated polynucleotide into a muscle of the mammal where the polynucleotide is taken up by the cells of the muscle and exerts a therapeutic effect on the mammal. The method can be used to deliver a therapeutic polypeptide to the cells of the mammal, to provide an immune response upon in vivo translation of the polynucleotide, to deliver antisense polynucleotides, to deliver receptors to the cells of the mammal or to provide transitory gene therapy.

Type: Grant

Filed: January 26, 1995

Date of Patent: December 31, 1996

Assignees: Vical Incorporated, Wisconsin Alumni Research Foundation

Inventors: Philip L. Felgner, Jon A. Wolff, Gary H. Rhodes, Robert W. Malone, Dennis A. Carson

- **Delivery of exogenous DNA sequences in a mammal**

Patent number: 5580859

Abstract: Polynucleotide sequences, comprising DNA and RNA molecules can be directly administered, for example by injection, to tissues, such as muscle, and expressed as a protein, polypeptide or polypeptide. The polynucleotides can be contained within liposomes or the polynucleotides can free from association with transfection-facilitating proteins, viral particles, liposomal formulations, charged lipids and calcium phosphate precipitating agents.

Type: Grant

Filed: March 18, 1994

Date of Patent: December 3, 1996

Assignees: VICAL Incorporated, Wisconsin Alumni Research Foundation

Inventors: Philip L. Felgner, Jon A. Wolff, Gary H. Rhodes, Robert W. Malone, Dennis A. Carson

- **Cationic transport reagents**

Patent number: 5527928

Abstract: For use in transporting biologically active species into and through membrane barriers, a symmetrical cationic diamine compound having the general structure
##STR1##

Type: Grant

Filed: September 30, 1994

Date of Patent: June 18, 1996

Inventors: Michael H. Nantz, Michael J. Bennett, Robert W. Malone

US Biolabs & Dr. Judy Mikovits (“Plandemic”¹³⁶)

When one looks into COVID, and the more one looks into it, it’s clear this is not “just another flu” but a seriously programmed biological weapon. The purpose of which, beyond “population control” (Bill Gates’ style), appears to be “lockstep” with a 1974 plan to depopulate the planet involving the Deep State and coordinated by the CIA¹³⁷ and the New World Order.¹³⁸

Worse, it might connect to World War III as the New Cold War gets going and already there is a battle, politically and conventionally (on the ground) for the US Biolabs which have been lied about on TV and in media, but testified about in fact, verbatim, in Congress. So the following pages will be listing those citation images as well:

¹³⁶ This and Dr. Malone’s interviews have been heavily censored by the Big Tech “Big Brother” in part of an Orwellian attempt to change history and obfuscate Dr. Fauci’s role in funding now known, defacto “gain-of-function” research on the manmade COVID in Wuhan labs. The original scientists in China have all been Renditioned by China, and are simply **gone**, though we have their names and social media account records they existed. In China, they can erase Tiananmen Square incidents, and even plan holidays at the square over the very area on the anniversary. That they crushed Hong Kong is not even talked about by Americans broadly. It’s a tragedy. But watching Dr. Fauci lie under oath to Hon. Senator Rand Paul and others about *not* doing gain of function when all experts and emails clearly show he did, was truly a sad day. Orwell was indeed correct in saying the future was “a boot stomping on your face, forever.”

¹³⁷ Let us not forget the CIA brought in, and was perhaps infiltrated by Nazis, because the Bush family itself has ties back to Prescott Bush, to the Nazi Party. George Bush Sr. was director of the CIA, and his son won a controversial election in 2000. However, what is interesting is that he is a secret society member of the infamous Yale “**Skull and Bones Society**.” His 2004 ‘opposition’ candidate, John Kerry (D), is also a known member of this group. The inquest of this was, in fact, the very reason the “Don’t Tase Me Bro” kid was tased (2007). He had asked many things, but once he asked that, Kerry’s handlers detained and attacked the college kid, and then he was publicly castigated for “making a scene.” But true to Operation: MOCKINGBIRD form... all media clips ever showed was a kid being tased, and never the question he had just previously asked. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r7Qef8oPmag>

¹³⁸ Trilateral Commission, founded 1973; speech of infamy:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8bdQwPyF2aE>

World Bank's: 'Population Planning' - "describes the Bank's efforts to help member countries reduce population growth rates" <http://archive.vn/ZNBRO>

I recently asked a panel of distinguished experts to review our activities in the population field within the World Bank.

They took a hard look at everything we have been doing since 1969, and they rightly reproached us for a tendency to treat population too much in isolation from our other activities.

In short, they asked us to think about the problem in a more comprehensive way—and deal with it accordingly.

They were right. And that is exactly what we plan to do.

Let me, now, summarize and conclude the central points I have made this evening.

importance. It would mean that the period of rapid acceleration in the rate of growth of the world's population has finally reached its peak and is now definitely moving downward towards stabilization.

But as welcome as this is, the fact remains that the current rate of decline in fertility in the developing countries is too slow to avoid their ultimately arriving at stationary populations far in excess of acceptable levels.

Unless governments, through appropriate policy action, can accelerate the reduction in fertility, the global population may not stabilize below 11 billion. That would be a world none of us would want to live in.

But governments can take action, and can accelerate the process, given the resolve and determination to do so.

The critical point is this: for every decade of delay in achieving a net reproduction rate of 1.0—replacement-level fertility—the ultimate steady-state world population will be approximately 15% greater.

Governments, then, must avoid the severe penalties of procrastination, and try to hasten the process forward.

The factors that appear to be the most important are: health, education, broadly distributed economic growth, urbanization, and the enhanced status of women.

These factors are at work in the developing world today, but their progress is too slow to be fully effective.

There are two broad categories of interventions that governments must undertake: those designed to encourage couples to desire smaller families; and those designed to provide parents with the means to implement that desire.

The first set of interventions sets out to alter the social and economic environment that tends to promote fertility, and by altering it to create a demand among parents for a new and smaller family norm.

And the second set of interventions supplies the requisite means that will make that new norm attainable.

To create the demand for a change in family norm, governments should try to:

- Reduce current infant and child mortality rates sharply.
- Expand basic education and substantially increase the proportion of girls in school.
- Increase the productivity of smallholders in the rural areas, and expand earning opportunities in the cities for low-income groups.
- Put greater stress on more equitable distribution of income and services in the drive for greater economic growth.
- And above all else, raise the status of women socially, economically, and politically.

To satisfy the demand for a change in family norms, governments and the international community should:

- Provide a broad choice of the present contraceptive techniques and services to parents.
- Improve the delivery systems by which parents can get the services they wish.
- And expand present levels of research seeking better techniques and services.

Both categories of interventions are necessary.

Recent studies confirm that the effect of family planning programs is greatest when they are joined to efforts designed to promote related social goals.

Figure 20 - World Bank depopulation plans, Kissinger Report¹³⁹; credit: archive.vn/ZNBRO

¹³⁹ https://archive.org/stream/NSSMHenryA.KissingerReport200435/NSSM%20Henry%20A.%20Kissinger%20Report%202004-35_djvu.txt

Frederick S. Jaffe (<http://archive.vn/vyqJ6>), vice president of Planned Parenthood Federation of America for John D. Rockefeller's "Population Council" NGO (<https://archive.vn/k59DM>)

PROPOSED MEASURES TO REDUCE FERTILITY, BY UNIVERSALITY OR SELECTIVITY OF IMPACT IN THE U.S.			
UNIVERSAL IMPACT	SELECTIVE IMPACT DEPENDING ON SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS		Measures Predicated on Existing Motivation to Prevent Unwanted Pregnancy
Social Constraints	Economic Deterrents/Incentives	Social Controls	
Restructure family: a) Postpone or avoid marriage b) Alter image of ideal family size Compulsory education of children Encourage increased homosexuality Educate for family limitation Fertility control agents in water supply Encourage women to work	Modify tax policies: a) Substantial marriage tax b) Child tax c) Tax married more than single d) Remove parents' tax exemption e) Additional taxes on parents with more than 1 or 2 children in school Reduce/eliminate paid maternity leave or benefits Reduce/eliminate children's or family allowances Bonuses for delayed marriage and greater child-spacing Pensions for women of 45 with less than N children Eliminate Welfare payments after first 2 children Chronic Depression Require women to work and provide few child care facilities Limit/eliminate publicly financed medical care, scholarships, housing, loans and subsidies to families with more than N children	Compulsory abortion of out-of-wedlock pregnancies Compulsory sterilization of all who have two children except for a few who would be allowed three Confine childbearing to only a limited number of adults Stock certificate permits for children Housing Policies: a) Discouragement of private home ownership b) Stop awarding public housing based on family size	Payments to encourage sterilization Payments to encourage contraception Payments to encourage abortion Abortion and sterilization on demand Allow harmless contraceptives to be distributed nonmedically Improve contraceptive technology Make contraception truly available and accessible Improve maternal health care, with family planning as a core element

Figure 21 - Planned Parenthood (known purveyors of genocide, and continued purveyors of eugenicide of Margaret Sanger), role in using feminism to destroy the family, presented to the Rockefeller Foundation (LOCKSTEP) NGO "Population Council"; credit: archive.vn/k59DM and F. Jaffe

"Kissinger Report" on population control, Conducted for US National Security Council (includes the CIA, military, etc.) <http://archive.vn/YVb7Q>

National Security Study Memorandum

NSSM 200

Implications of Worldwide Population Growth
For U.S. Security and Overseas Interests
(THE KISSINGER REPORT)

December 10, 1974

Part Two --	Policy Recommendations	73
Section I	A U.S. Global Population Strategy	74-84
Section II	Action to Create Conditions for Fertility Decline: Population and a Development Assistance Strategy	85-105
	A. General Strategy and Resource for A.I.D. Assistance	85-91
	B. Functional Assistance Programs to Create Conditions for Fertility Decline	92-102

2. Research, experimentation and evaluation of ongoing programs should focus on answering the questions (such as those raised above, relating to female education) that determine what steps can and should be taken in other sectors that will in a cost-effective manner speed up the rate of fertility decline. In addition to the five areas discussed in Section II. B 1-5 below, the research should also cover the full range of factors affecting fertility, such as laws and norms respecting age of marriage, and financial incentives. Work of this sort should be undertaken in individual key countries to determine the motivational factors required there to develop a preference for small family size. High priority must be given to testing feasibility and replicability on a wide scale.

3. Expanding Wage Employment Opportunities, Especially for Women

Discussion

Employment is the key to access to income, which opens the way to improved health, education, nutrition, and reduced family size. Reliable job opportunities enable parents to limit their family size and invest in the welfare of the children they have.

4. Developing Alternatives to the Social Security Role Provided By Children to Aging Parents

Discussion:

In most LDCs the almost total absence of government or other institutional forms of social security for old people forces dependence on children for old age survival. The need for such support appears to be one of the important motivations for having numerous children. otherwise bear). Proposals have been made for son-insurance (provided to the parents if they have no more than three children), and for deferred payments of retirement benefits (again tied to

1. Providing Minimal Levels of Education, Especially for Women

Discussion

There is fairly convincing evidence that female education especially of 4th grade and above correlates strongly with reduced desired family size, although it is unclear the extent to which the female education causes reductions in desired family size or whether it is a faster pace of development which leads both to increased demand for female education and to reduction in desired family size. There is also a relatively widely held theory -- though not statistically

5. Pursuing Development Strategies that Skew Income Growth Toward the Poor, Especially Rural Development Focussing on Rural Poverty

Income distribution and rural development: The higher a family's income, the fewer children it will probably have, except at the very top of the income scale. Similarly, the more evenly distributed the income in a society, the lower the overall fertility rate seems to be since better income distribution means that the poor, who have the highest fertility, have higher income.

6. Concentration on Education and Indoctrination of Children Regarding the Desirability of Smaller Family Size

Therefore, family planning supply (contraceptive technology and delivery systems) and demand (the motivation for reduced fertility) would not be viewed as mutually exclusive alternatives; they are complementary and may be mutually reinforcing.

Short-term approaches: These approaches include improvement and field testing of existing technology and development of new technology. It is expected that some of these approaches would be ready for use within five years. Specific short term approaches worthy of increased effort are as follows:

- Oral contraceptives have become popular and widely used; yet the optimal steroid hormone combinations and doses for LDC populations need further definition. Field studies in several settings are required. Approx. Increased Cost: \$3 million annually.
 - Intra-uterine devices of differing size, shape, and bioactivity should be developed and tested to determine the optimum levels of effectiveness, safety, and acceptability. Approx. Increased Cost: \$3 million annually.
 - Sterilization of men and women has received wide-spread acceptance in several areas when a simple, quick, and safe procedure is readily available. Female sterilization has been improved by technical advances with laparoscopes, culdoscopes, and greatly simplifies abdominal surgical techniques. Further improvements by the use of tubal clips, trans-cervical approaches, and simpler techniques can be developed. For men several current techniques hold promise but require more refinement and evaluation. Approx. Increased Cost \$6 million annually.
 - Injectable contraceptives for women which are effective for three months or more and are administered by para-professionals undoubtedly will be a significant improvement. Currently available methods of this type are limited by their side effects and potential hazards. There are reasons to believe that these problems can be overcome with additional research. Approx. Increased Cost: \$5 million annually.
 - Leuteolytic and anto-progesterone approaches to fertility control including use of prostaglandins are theoretically attractive but considerable work remains to be done. Approx. Increased Cost: \$7 million annually.
- Clinics or centres run by private organizations (e.g., family planning associations);
 - Commercial channels which in many countries sell condoms, oral contraceptives, and sometimes spermicidal foam over the counter;
 - Private physicians.

Commercial Channels. In an increasing number of LDCs, contraceptives (such as condoms, foam and the Pill) are being made available without prescription requirements through commercial channels such as drugstores.* The commercial approach offers a practical, low-cost means of providing family planning services, since it utilizes an existing distribution system and does not involve financing the further expansion of public clinical delivery facilities.

NATO and Eastern Europe. In the west, only France and Greece have a policy of increasing population growth -- which the people are successfully disregarding. (In a recent and significant change from traditional positions, however, the French Assembly overwhelmingly endorsed a law not only authorizing general availability of contraceptives but also providing that their cost be borne by the social security system.) Other western NATO members have no policies. Most provide some or substantial family planning services. All appear headed toward lower growth rates. In two NATO member countries (West Germany and Luxembourg), annual numbers of deaths already exceed births, yielding a negative natural growth rate.

Romania, Hungary, Bulgaria, and Czechoslovakia have active policies to increase their population growth rates despite the reluctance of their people to have larger families. Within the USSR, fertility rates in RSFSR and the republics of Ukraine, Latvia, and Estonia are below replacement level. This situation has prevailed at least since 1969-1970 and, if continued, will eventually lead to negative population growth in these republics. In the United States, average fertility also fell below replacement level in the past two years (1972 and 1973). There is a

6. Concentration on Education and Indoctrination of Children Regarding the Desirability of Smaller Family Size

Figure 22 - "Kissinger Report" on population Control, USNSC (a Deep State rogue agency), 1974; credit: archive.vn/YVb7Q

Ukraine’s US-funded Biolabs¹⁴⁰

Figure 23 - US embassy page about Biological Threat Reduction Program; credit: opindia.com¹⁴¹

These are the scrubbed Embassy fact documents about the “non-existent” or “alleged” bio-labs:

1. [Interim Central Reference Laboratory - Pomirky Region](#)
2. [Luhansk 9a](#)
3. [Dnipropetrovsk](#)
4. [Veterinary Program](#)
5. [Vinnitsia](#)
6. [Kherson](#)
7. [Ternopil](#)
8. [Uzhgorod](#)
9. [Lviv Oblast](#)
10. [Promislova Str. Lviv](#)
11. [EIDSS - Georgia](#)

¹⁴⁰ https://www.algora.com/Algora_blog/2022/02/24/the-secret-us-biolabs-in-ukraine

¹⁴¹ <https://www.opindia.com/2022/03/usa-admits-biolabs-in-ukraine-says-biological-attack-russias-fault/>

12. [PACS](#)

13. [Inst. of Veterinary Medicine](#)

>>If they have nothing to hide, why delete the files in the first place?<<

Figure 24 - 11 Pentagon Controlled (allegedly) Biolabs; credit: Dr. J. Santiano¹⁴²

“Even though the Biosafety labs (BSL) are in Ukraine, Ukrainians are prohibited from disclosing publicly any sensitive information about the US program.

The US military program is sensitive information

Ukraine has no control over the military bio-laboratories on its own territory. According to the 2005 Agreement between the US DoD and the Ministry of Health of Ukraine the Ukrainian government is prohibited from public disclosure of sensitive information about the US program and Ukraine is obliged to transfer to the US Department of Defense (DoD) dangerous pathogens for biological research. The Pentagon has been granted access to certain state secrets of Ukraine in connection with the projects under their agreement.

Biowarfare scientists under diplomatic cover

Among the set of bilateral agreements between the US and Ukraine is the establishment of the Science and Technology Center in Ukraine (STCU) – an International organization funded mainly by the US government which has been accorded diplomatic status. The

¹⁴² <https://drjessesantiano.com/pentagon-bio-laboratories-in-ukraine/>

STCU officially supports projects of scientists previously involved in the Soviet biological weapons program.

Over the past 20 years the STCU has invested over \$285 million in funding and managing some 1,850 projects of scientists who previously worked on the development of weapons of mass destruction.

Living near BSL labs can be hazardous, mainly when lab leaks occur.

Infectious diseases surrounding the Biolabs

364 Ukrainians died from Swine Flu

One of the Pentagon laboratories is located in Kharkiv, where in January 2016 at least 20 Ukrainian soldiers died from Flu-like virus in just two days with 200 more being hospitalized.

The Ukrainian government did not report on the dead Ukrainian soldiers in Kharkiv. As of March 2016 364 deaths have been reported across Ukraine (81.3 % caused by Swine Flu A (H1N1) pdm09 – the same strain which caused the world pandemic in 2009).

Police investigate infections with incurable diseases.

A highly suspicious Hepatitis A infection spread rapidly in just a few months across South East Ukraine where most of the Pentagon Biolabs are located.

37 people have been hospitalized for Hepatitis A in the Ukrainian city of Mykolaiv as of January 2018. Local police have launched an investigation into “infection with human immunodeficiency virus and other incurable diseases”.

Three years ago more than 100 people in the same city became infected with Cholera. Both diseases are alleged to have spread through contaminated drinking water.

In the summer of 2017 60 people with Hepatitis A were admitted to hospital in the city of Zaporizhia, the cause of this outbreak is still unknown.

In the Odessa region, 19 children from an orphanage were hospitalized for hepatitis A in June 2017.

29 cases of Hepatitis A were reported in Kharkiv in November 2017. The virus was isolated in contaminated drinking water. One of the Pentagon bio-labs is located in Kharkiv which was blamed for the deadly Flu outbreak a year ago which claimed the lives of 364 Ukrainians.“

Figure 26 - Information about diseases spreading near to biolabs

Проведение исследований в обход международных обязательств

6

Ежегодные отчетные документы США и Украины о выполнении Конвенции о запрещении разработки, производства и накопления запасов бактериологического (биологического) и токсинного оружия и об их уничтожении

В ежегодно представляемых в ООН материалах США и Украины сознательно умалчивается о реализации военно-биологических проектов на территории Украины

8.4 Источники финансирования. Национальная академия аграрных наук Украины.

Форма А, часть 2 II)

Национальные программы исследований и разработок в области биологической защиты

Объявлять нечего

В октябре 2010 года президент США Б.Обама признал факт противоправных действий своей страны и принёс официальные извинения президенту Гватемалы Альваро Коломе. В 1946-1948 годах специалисты США заражали социально незащищенных граждан Гватемалы (заключенных) возбудителями сифилиса и гонореи. Всего были инфицированы более 1500 человек.

Figure 28 - Documents asserting STD spread related to US foreign Biolabs, this time in Guatemala

The author acknowledges the former as propaganda. The thing is, what makes one of the “Three Powers” (1984) propaganda worse than the others if they are telling some of the truth, and the former is obfuscating it, and directing Ukrainians to burn records?¹⁴⁴

Figure 29 - (Below) - Unclassified NCDC documents from US Government

¹⁴⁴ <https://gab.com/stillnessinthestorm/posts/107855469365983853>

UNCLASSIFIED

Risk of Emerging Infections from Insectivorous Bats in Ukraine and Georgia. Denys Muzyka (NSC IECVM), Lela Urushadze (NCDC) and Andres Velasco-Villa (US CDC), HDTRA1-14-24-FRCWMD-BAA

Objectives: Detecting of emerging viral (coronaviruses, filoviruses, paramyxoviruses, orthomyxoviruses, lyssaviruses) bacterial (*Brucella* spp, *Leptospira* spp, *Yersinia* spp) pathogens important for human and animal health in bats in Ukraine, Georgia; Investigating how landscape biodiversity changes influence the relative composition of endemic viral and bacterial agents in bat populations, as well as assess their eco-evolutionary linkages with disease emergence in humans and domestic animals; Build a sustainable harmonized surveillance network for the early detection, full genomic characterization of high consequence agents associated with bat populations in Ukraine, Georgia.

Method: Integration of a multidisciplinary, interagency coalition of premier public health, veterinary institutions and Universities to foster the creation of a regional, self sustainable multinational coalition for the early detection, typing, development of a high-level analytical framework to provide adequate interpretation of findings.

Status of effort: This proposal will be conducted and integrated by a coordinated persistent effort of principal investigators from NSC IECVM, NCDC, US CDC in collaboration with Virginia Tech and USGS. Expected findings are of interest for the fields of ecology, evolution of infectious bacterial and viral diseases, early warning systems, and global human and animals health.

Personnel Supported: More than 60 scientists from USA, Ukraine, Georgia with either PhD, Master graduate and/or undergraduate degrees with more than 10 years of experience will participate on field activity, diagnostics, molecular typing, Sanger sequencing, next generation sequencing, bio-informatics, ecology niche modeling, data visualization.

Publications & Meetings: We anticipate active participation in at least one per year peer reviewed scientific publications and participation two scientific meetings at year.

Y1. SOPs implementation for biosecure bat capture, sampling, processing for detection, typing, sequencing, niche modeling; field and laboratory activity. **Y2.** Continuing field and laboratory activity; development of analytical pipelines for comparative genomics and ecological niche modeling, QA/QC implementation algorithms and trouble shooting. **Y3.** Sustainability assessment and implementation completion phase, final data analyses, data visualizations, presentation of future directions.

Funding: Y2020-2023 Total Ukraine–Georgia \$1600K/3 years: \$207-398K/year IECVM, \$178-257K/year NCDC, \$53K/year STCU. Total CDC coalition \$1,554,519/3 years: \$512K-527K/year.

Contact information: Dr. D. Muzyka, dmuzyka77@gmail.com, +380673855798; Dr. L. Urushadze, lelincdc@gmail.com +995599245434. Dr. Andres Velasco-Villa, dly3@cdc.gov; phone: 404 639 1055.

UNCLASSIFIED

The Conjunction of Government, Science, and Science Media

This would not be a complete report without describing the money trails of the “fact check triangle”¹⁴⁵ and the more repugnant triangle (if that is possible), between government (and Academia receiving grants¹⁴⁶), the scientists and programs that restrict wholesome science and perform monstrous experiments, or useless ones, or secret ones that only power the US Military Empire, and finally the web of media pundits: journals, first tier reporting sites, and hack media sites which often (in a bizarre game of telephone) sensationalize, misreport, and are used to hype up anything (especially Climate Change and the Cult of Einstein, like General Relativity, black holes, etc.) that encourages public support for the lies and propaganda.

Figure 30 - “the Ministry of Truth”, “1984”; credit: G. Orwell

¹⁴⁵

<https://www.uschamberfoundation.org/bhq/industry-academia-and-government-collaboration-game-changer-us-economic-future>

¹⁴⁶ Public institutions are government owned/operated and they receive \$1.068 trillion in grants and federal endowments, etc., annually, in the United States alone.

<https://datalab.usaspending.gov/colleges-and-universities/>

The Fact-check Triangle, aka the “Ministry of Truth”¹⁴⁷

After the 2016 election of populist President Donald J. Trump defeating the NWO handpicked choice, Hillary Clinton¹⁴⁸, Google, Facebook, and eventually Twitter got together as part of an effort to directly influence elections. They did so in 2018¹⁴⁹ and 2020¹⁵⁰, respectively. Although, the 2020 election was clearly stolen in key states with Google Trends spikes in search terms like “election fraud” and “jail time for election fraud”, particularly in Pennsylvania where Biden had destroyed his campaign by attacking coal and natural gas, the main issue for these Orwellian **public** companies (who act as publishers and not platforms) is not how to steal elections. That was Biden’s¹⁵¹ campaign’s job and the DNC machine itself. It is, solely, “can we use algorithms and advertising restrictions, language control and selective policing to control people and influence voters?” The answer was given beforehand by one - to his credit Democrat - scientist¹⁵²: yes. Yes, it can and it was done.¹⁵³

Figure 31 - Wisconsin 2020 Election fraud;
credit: theburningplatform.com ¹⁵⁴

But what is less known to the public is the power of the growing post 2016 movement known as “fact-checking.” It’s become an industry of its own¹⁵⁵. Here’s how it works^{156,157}

¹⁴⁷ One cannot help but think of Deloris Umbridge’s torture of Potter and the other kids, “I will not tell lies” quill... while she herself was a secret supporter of you-know-who and a liar and saboteur.

¹⁴⁸ Russian colluder, purchaser of Steele Dossier (fake propaganda), negligent killer of Ambassador Stevens, liar under oath, victimizer of her husband’s abused female victims, and known associate of over 60 people who “committed suicide” under incredibly mysterious circumstances. Yeah, she’s a real gem.

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oix729kTwHq>

¹⁵⁰

<https://legalinsurrection.com/2020/11/big-tech-manipulated-2020-election-googles-search-results-were-strongly-biased-in-favor-of-liberals-and-democrats/>

¹⁵¹ “We’re in a situation where we have put together, and you guys did it for President Obama’s administration before this, we have put together, I think, **the most extensive and inclusive voter fraud organization in the history of American politics**,” Biden said during a campaign event.

<http://freebeacon.com/elections/biden-we-have-the-most-extensive-and-inclusive-voter-fraud-organization>

>>There is no context in which this can be spun. It reads and sounds exactly as it is, rare honesty.<<

¹⁵² Dr. Robert Epstein

¹⁵³ Figure 31 is impossible to explain in any other manner than pure manipulation.

¹⁵⁴ The author is upset Trump gave up so easily, whatever Democrats say happened. The fact is that the whole world knew it was fraud, and he surrendered. Now the world suffers. That is unacceptable, and as Biden is a traitor, Trump is also a failure, and unfit to be President of the United States after 2020/2021’s events. Only China/Russia won the 2020 election.

¹⁵⁵ <https://nypost.com/2021/12/14/facebook-admits-the-truth-fact-checks-are-really-just-lefty-opinion/>

¹⁵⁶ Try searching “fact check triangle glenn beck” on Google, you will get nothing from his own website or show, but plenty of critics of his, from the Left. That’s internal confirmation of the hypothesis. Ergo: we use duckduckgo.com

¹⁵⁷ It’s more than a little disingenuous that Facebook claims “*Since we do not believe that a private company like Facebook should be the arbiters of truth, we rely on fact-checkers to identify, review and rate potential misinformation across Facebook, Instagram and WhatsApp.*”

Table 3 - Companies of the IFCN¹⁵⁸, and their owners

<i>IFCN Company</i>	<i>Owner</i>	<i>Source/Other Notes</i>
Politifact	Poynter Institute	Media Studies, Inc. ¹⁵⁹
Factcheck.org	Annenberg PPC of U. of Pa.	
Lead Stories	China ¹⁶⁰ /Tik tok	Trendolizer
Science Feedback ¹⁶¹	Non-profit from France	Climate Feedback/ Health Fb
AP Factchecker	Associated Press (non-profit)	Unions, CWA/AFL-CIO
AFP Fact Check	AFP (France)	
Reuters Fact Check	UK/Reuters (BBC?)	Thomson Corporation (Canada)
Full Fact	Google, Soros, eBay/Omidyar	Used by all the big tech
Check Your Fact	Daily Caller (Fox/T. Carlson)	Tucker has sold his stake
Fact Checker by Washington Post	Jeff Bezos/Amazon	Washington Post is extremely leftist, unabashedly
The Sunlight Foundation	Center for Responsive Politics	OpenSecrets/Democracy Fund
Ballotpedia	Lucy Burns Institute	State Policy Network
Snopes	Snopes Media Group	James Randi Eedu. and Soros
*Media Bias Fact Check	Dav Van Zandt	

* Palmer Report criticizes it as a one man show. For example it rates Poynter as left-center relatively unbiased, but its own page poll¹⁶² reveals most, by far, feel Poynter is a left leaning source (64% vs. 31%).

Note - the maroon above indicates communism oriented, not deeper right. By far, then, the top fact checkers out there are left leaning. The darker the blue the left-leaning it is.

For starters, Facebook is public. Secondly, the IFCN companies are all private, and have no auditors. Finally, everyone, especially Facebook knows it is censoring and lying about it. So the charade is incredibly confusing. It's best to just avoid such companies, as they are nothing but trouble.

¹⁵⁸ <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/2020/04/12/the-10-best-fact-checking-websites-for-2020/>

¹⁵⁹ Koch, Sorors, other elites

¹⁶⁰

<https://www.newswars.com/facebook-fact-checker-lead-stories-funded-by-controversial-chinese-company-that-owns-tiktok/>

¹⁶¹ "Each fact checker holds a Ph.D. and has recently published articles in top-tier peer-reviewed science journals." Case closed. What is hilarious to the author is that scientists and regular people even do not see the problem in this.

¹⁶² <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/poynter-institute/>

Few, if any, of the above organizations can be called objective. Note that all of them receive money, for or non-profit, for their “efforts” to sway the narrative.

The FACT CHECK TRIANGLE

Figure 32 - the Fact Check Triangle” [[MK-ULTRA on large scale¹⁶³]] mind-control/propaganda machine; bear in mind this machine is a doubling agent for the power and potency of the Military Industrial Complex; credit: author

The fact remains that this triangle is incredibly deceptive and without audit. It ran afoul of the journals in the COVID¹⁶⁴ and vaccine situation as “misinformation”¹⁶⁵ which protected corporate

¹⁶³ See also: Operation MOCKINGBIRD <https://allthatsinteresting.com/operation-mockingbird>

¹⁶⁴ <https://www.bmj.com/content/376/bmj.o95>

¹⁶⁵ <https://bookthepit.com/bmj-vs-facebook/>

power and money came into rare conflict with medical scientists who, in this case, really desired the truth to exist. Or, at least, a politically correct version of the truth, which wouldn't run them afoul of the irascible autocrat Dr. Fauci, who is, as of this writing, curiously missing Epstein style. Fewer people know, even, that the fact-checkers work in tandem, but all took their cue from the innocently enough started "Snopes" which sold out and went corporate many years ago.¹⁶⁶ However its model rating system has become such a cultural icon, people began to assume that if a mainstream media outlet said "mostly false" or "incorrect" that this means it was in fact that way. However, several instances of "don't believe your lying eyes" have occurred, with such blatant mental gymnastics, that now the entire fact check triangle has fallen under suspicion (rightly so) by the right as merely a fascist, tyrannical con. The fact that many forms of "misinformation" appear to be opinions, which are free speech; and that many forms of "hate speech" are also patently free speech according to the Supreme Court of the United States¹⁶⁷, and the US Constitution and Bill of Rights, has caused most people to begin leaving mainstream social media.¹⁶⁸ A plethora of new platforms have evolved. Separately, Facebook had the worst earnings report and stock price crash by total \$\$ amount in history, in Q1 2022 (nearly \$250 billion).¹⁶⁹

Just as the COVID and fact-check triangle train, metaverse, and Dr. Fauci's emails came to light, suddenly the New Cold War began with Trudeau taking tyrannical control of cryptocurrency and commerce in Canada¹⁷⁰, and then Russia pounced on Ukraine like a hungry lion.¹⁷¹

- Fauci's original emails leaked June 6, 2021
- COVID Fact-check fiasco Jan 11, 2022
- Facebook loses record value, Feb 3, 2022
- Metaverse Failure Feb 4, 2022
- Dr. Fauci Emails surface about gain-of-function Feb 15, 2022
- Trudeau (Fidel Castro's son) seizes dictatorial control in Canada Feb 15, 2022
 - Revoked Feb 22, 2022
- Russia invades Ukraine Feb 24, 2022
- US/Ukraine burns lab documents early March 2022

That is where things stand as of this writing, but there is something more to say about the 'circle jerk' known as the Fact-check Triangle. For starters, it is not going away. Now that the ESG score exists, the author expects it to become governmental and therefore the Nazi's fascism to arrive. Already socialists have infiltrated the government in promoting segregation etc. It is

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.npr.org/2017/07/26/539576135/fact-checking-website-snopes-is-fighting-to-stay-alive>

¹⁶⁷ https://www.huffpost.com/entry/1a-victory-scotus-again-confirms-hate-speech-is_b_594a78a0e4b0d799132a164e

¹⁶⁸ <https://theconversation.com/why-people-leave-facebook-and-what-it-tells-us-about-the-future-of-social-media-128952>

¹⁶⁹ <https://www.npr.org/2022/02/03/1077820355/facebooks-transition-to-metaverse-has-eaten-into-the-social-media-giants-profits>

¹⁷⁰ www.coindesk.com/policy/2022/02/15/canadas-trudeau-enacts-emergencies-act-and-crypto-is-included/

¹⁷¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Timeline_of_the_2022_Russian_invasion_of_Ukraine

expected, therefore, that the natural outcome of these movements is a “divide and conquer,” as the author already predicted, elsewhere.

The second thing that the reader must understand about these secret empires, the NWO, the Deep State, the obfuscation of science, etc., is that it is motivated not only by money (yours and not yours, which is more poignant, actually, and not only by power/force, but access, influence, and affluence. Therefore the fact-check triangle is a clever, even diabolical scheme which is paid via subsidy to promote lying, mind-control, population control, protect the peddles or poison and pedophilia, and keep the real Science from ever reaching the public. In other words, all real fact checking is a threat to this ‘triangle of truth’ because at each stage of the triangle is a vested interest: NGO or institution, agency, etc.

There is only going to be an acceleration of this lying apparatus because it has no massively funded natural enemy. So it is vital that the reader do their own homework, and indeed, fact check for yourself this document, and any other.

The Unholy Marriage of Fascism and Science (Here is your Nazi Conspiracy)

The public has suspected a party of institutional racism and of support of Nazis and Communists and the results are in: it is 100% without a doubt the DNC, puppets of the Trilateral Commission and NWO, and their RINO (Republican in Name Only) partners across the aisle selling out the People and the world for self power.

However, how does this fascist, totalitarian system work? Who is in charge? Do they even agree with one another? Are they building one New World Order, or has it fractured? What is the likely outcome of squabbling over resources, territory, power, and prestige as the “king of the hill” topples? Who gets this power? How widespread are the RINOs and how many Democratic operatives are working for/with China and/or Russia? Is China using the US as a puppet to fight its rival in Russia? Are we headed for a “Three Kingdoms”¹⁷² experience? Will Europe really devolve into a third world war? Who is in the New Axis?

Finally: what role, if any, does the Military Industrial Complex and its scientific-technocratic partnership play, and why does the media ‘run cover’ and protect these interests? We know they do, because David Rockefeller himself thanked the media for joining in the enterprise.

It is beyond the purview of this paper to consider Salla’s proposition, that a Dark Fleet/Deep State alien hypothesis has humanity at each other’s throats ever since we broadcasted into space in the 1930s. However, seeing the Milgrom and other experiments we can clearly see that Holocausts are a very real and likely outcome of certain thought patterns and behaviors.

Therefore we must ask, if the media will not tell the scientific “whole truth, and nothing but the truth,” who then can we trust for truth? Religion would automatically provide an answer, except the problem has spread there, too, and corruption is as rampant worldwide as within the Christian circles. Wherever money, power, and prestige flow, corruption is easily found, and conspiracy. The main conspiracies are to defraud. The next are to control the narrative and protect/project certain optics. Why? Lies work. Studies show lies are effective, while the truth is known to bruise egos. Many scientists have thrown away failed experiments, saddened by their

¹⁷² “Romance of the Three Kingdoms”; here watch the series:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WNHnX4xsplo&list=PL33A390995E9A7F00>

failures, so they outright lie rather than risk exposure. But throwing out data is also a lie: it denies the truth to the public.

There is no truth more conspiratorially obfuscated than the simple fact:

- ❖ Electricity, not gravity, runs the Universe¹⁷³. It is the PEM force which is the real one, and gravity is but a shadow or reflection of the behaviors of charges and fields.

This is not a fact that is in dispute in small circles, or among a pint at a pub, etc. But put an astrophysicist on stage, or give him a pen and paper (so to speak), and he will wax into long discourses about abstruse math which only he (or she) can understand. This type of backbiting is common among socialists, and it is a clear reflection of the infiltration of ideologies of liars into academia. But, with the amount of money and grants involved, and the fame of press, TV, even movies and biopics which immortalize one almost as a god, we see a serious truth unfold: corruption goes beyond ideology.

There is no doubt, for example, that Einstein was a smart man. The precise details of why he paid his wife his Nobel money¹⁷⁴, or how he knew he'd win that money, may never be known. But it doesn't take much to understand she gave him inside knowledge into the community¹⁷⁵, and that Poincare had died without strong credit for his unique ideas of Relativity and Gravity Waves. Put these things together, and you have ample reason enough for a smart man to commit a smart con. It only cost him several thousands of hush money to his ex wife, and he was afterwards an immortal of Science. There is no name more rigorously defended, tooth and nail, despite all evidence, and with simply hyper-exaggerated emphasis, than Albert Einstein's. By extension one would think that Hawking had solved cancer itself. In point of fact, even his Hawking radiation was wrong¹⁷⁶, let alone his ideas of black holes.¹⁷⁷

Why do media outlets get away with publishing this? It is, again, a triangle... but at the top is a rain of 'mana' in the form of government money. Not only that, but no one wants to end their career in obscurity or by being eliminated by a hateful mob of scientists in journals. Therefore, it is a Pavlov's Dog scenario. If the media barks, the scientists give them a bone. If the scientists bark, the government gives them a bone. If the government barks, the media puts out propaganda, and the taxpayers give the government a bone (or fail to stop owned politicians from doing so). If all three bark, people wear masks which do not stop people from getting COVID¹⁷⁸, or inject themselves with boosters which do not work, and then demand fascistic control of others and this gives the government another bone: your freedoms. Freedom is never more than a generation away from disappearing.

¹⁷³ For God? Is God? The mythic records are sporadic in their descriptions of "the Lord" at times, if it is not a star or later, YHVH (Jove/Jupiter)

¹⁷⁴ http://content.time.com/time/specials/packages/article/0,28804,1848817_1848816_1848815,00.html

¹⁷⁵ She was a mathematician

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.nature.com/articles/news040712-12>

¹⁷⁷

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/startswithabang/2020/07/09/yes-stephen-hawking-lied-to-us-all-about-how-black-holes-decay/>

¹⁷⁸ <https://fee.org/articles/new-danish-study-finds-masks-don-t-protect-wearers-from-covid-infection/>

Table 4 - List of Outlets, Owners, Partners, and Government or Other Connections

Outlet	Journals	Gov. / Partners	Other Information
phys.org	ScienceX ¹⁷⁹	UK	
Nature ¹⁸⁰	Springer Nature	UK	Macmillan Publishing
Space.com	Live Science	[media syndicates]	Future via Purch
IFL Science		UK / LabX Media Group (Canada)	The Scientist
Science Daily, LLC		Jackson Laboratory?	Dan and Michele Hogan
SciTechDaily	NE Journal of Medicine		Vicki Hyde/DailyEDeals
EurekAlert!	AAAS	USE / Academia in general	Network Solutions LLC

How Many of These Have Connections to Socialists (NaZis), Communists, and Autocrats of the Military Industrial Complex?

Not unlike the de facto funding of Black Lives Matter © by Soros and China¹⁸¹, [the funneling of money through the various Democrat related companies in and off shore¹⁸², and the relation of all of these to the DSA's "Sunrise Movement"¹⁸³ which took advantage of G. Floyd's death to pre-arrange segregated 'spontaneous' riots and movements...] **money trails exist between corporations and government.**¹⁸⁴ We know even without looking such connections exists,

¹⁷⁹ <https://phys.org/journals/>

¹⁸⁰ "On 30 October 2008, *Nature* endorsed an American presidential candidate for the first time when it supported Barack Obama during his campaign in America's 2008 presidential election."
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nature_%28journal%29

¹⁸¹ "Thousand Currents" is the laundering company <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=45Ats25bktI>

¹⁸² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TLBMhdLV0jI>

¹⁸³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DgsnyHILdb8>

¹⁸⁴ "They want your retirement money. They want it back so they can give it to their criminal friends on Wall Street, and you know something? They'll get it. They'll get it all from you, sooner or later, 'cause they own this fucking place. It's a big club, and you ain't in it. You and I are not in the big club. And by the way, it's the same big club they use to beat you over the head with all day long when they tell you what to believe. All day long beating you over the head in their media telling you what to believe, what to think and what to buy. The table is tilted folks. The game is rigged, and nobody seems to notice, nobody seems to care. Good honest hard-working people -- white collar, blue collar, it doesn't matter what color shirt you have on -- good honest hard-working people continue -- these are people of modest means -- continue to

because of the simultaneous deplatforming of Alex Jones in 2018¹⁸⁵ (for elections¹⁸⁶) and with his money vendors¹⁸⁷. Yet, look we will, anyways¹⁸⁸.

Table 5 - Government and Military, and Corporate Contract Connections

Corporate Contractor	Value of contracts (\$M) or Revenue	Government Agency Connections	Military or other Partnerships
Blackwater (Academi)	(private) R=\$800?	CIA	Navy, USMC
Halliburton	R=\$23995	US D.O.D. (Cheney)	Nigeria and Oil
Rolls Royce ¹⁸⁹	\$945, R=\$52150	British Aerospace, RAF	China, Airbus, Boeing
Boeing	\$28089, R=\$62290	US D.O.D.	NASA
Lockheed-Martin	\$48666, R=\$65400	US D.O.D.	USAF, USMC, Navy
Raytheon	\$16351, R=\$56580	US D.O.D.	USAF
Airbus	R=\$52150	Worldwide	EADS
General Dynamics	\$20961, R=\$39350	US D.O.D., UK, Saudi	Army, Navy
Northrop Grumman	\$16101, R=\$35667	US D.O.D., NATO, UK	USAF
Honeywell	\$6364, R=\$34392	US D.O.D.	NASA, USAF
GE Company	\$3528, R=\$74196	US. D.O.D.	United Nations
McKesson	\$9640, R=\$231051	UK, Canada, Germany	[they make RFIDs]
Leidos	\$7272, R=\$18569	US D.O.D., DHS, [intel]	Los Alamos Labs

* There are hundreds of military contractors, and thousands of US government contractors alone; here we just showcase some of the more infamous or famous ones.

elect these rich cocksuckers who don't give a fuck about them." (sic) ~G. Carlin

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Nyvxt1svxso>

¹⁸⁵

https://www.reddit.com/r/conspiracy/comments/97j390/unpacking_the_deplatforming_of_alex_jones_an/

¹⁸⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PqeLwH1vf_4

¹⁸⁷ Which would ostensibly be a RICO fraud case, if investigated and prosecuted. Probably as wire fraud.

¹⁸⁸ Imagine what a thorough data mining of the Panama Papers scandal, and wikileaks, would reveal.

<https://panamapapers.sueddeutsche.de/articles/56febff0a1bb8d3c3495adf4/>

¹⁸⁹ Sold its nuclear divestments to Westinghouse Electric in 2019

Table 6 - Most famous National Labs and US/UK/EU Government Connections

Lab, Location	Government Connections	Funding in \$M	Other Info or Secret Programs (current)
Los Alamos	US D.O. Energy	\$3,875	Secret City: Project Y
JPL	NASA, USAF, USSF	\$2,600 ¹⁹⁰	CERCLA
DARPA	US D.O. Defense	\$3,427	Boeing X-37, etc. ¹⁹¹
CERN	U.N. ¹⁹²	\$1,171	LHC, ATLAS, ALICE
LIGO	Univ. of CalTech	\$45 ¹⁹³	
Stanford	Stanford U., USDOE	\$2,476 ¹⁹⁴	SLAC NAL
Fermilab	USDOE/OAS	\$546	Muon G-2, ICARUS
INFN	Italy, Germany, EU	~\$265 ¹⁹⁵	LABEC ¹⁹⁶
Palomar Observatory	Univ. of CalTech	\$2,840 (University)	
Sandia Z Machine	Nat. Nucl. Security A.	\$3,600	Lockheed-Martin ¹⁹⁷
Oak Ridge NL	USDOE	\$2,400	US Army CoE ¹⁹⁸
Quantum CDC	Google	\$5,850 (all Quantum)	Lab X ¹⁹⁹

¹⁹⁰ https://d2pn8kiwq2w21t.cloudfront.net/documents/Annual_Report_-_2020.pdf

¹⁹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/DARPA#Active_projects

¹⁹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/CERN>

¹⁹³ https://www.nsf.gov/about/budget/fy2021/pdf/40i_fy2021.pdf

¹⁹⁴ https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2020/02/f72/doe-fy2021-laboratory-table_1.pdf

¹⁹⁵ <https://indico.cells.es/event/26/attachments/389/522/INFN.pdf>

¹⁹⁶ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1140/epjp/s13360-021-01411-1>

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.sandia.gov/app/uploads/sites/81/2021/07/labnews07-10-15.pdf>

¹⁹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Oak_Ridge_National_Laboratory

¹⁹⁹

<https://thequantuminsider.com/2020/02/05/googles-secret-quantum-project-team-x-working-on-something-special/>

Figure 33 - Los Alamos Budget Allocation; nearly $\frac{3}{4}$ of funds go to weapons programs; credit: lanl.gov²⁰⁰

²⁰⁰ <https://www.lanl.gov/about/facts-figures/budget.php>

But wait, there's more! The Unbelievable waste of National Science Foundation

The author comes from a state with a story of two very different Senators. One is controlled by a Chinese princess, and is renowned for his cocaine use, and looking like a turtle. The other is a staunch libertarian who filibusters, and stands up against liars like Dr. A. Fauci. One of his other stunts is to regale the Senate with explanations of *how they waste money* funding absolutely worthless science.²⁰¹ The National Science Foundation²⁰² is known for giving grants to some of the worst porkbelly science on the planet. Here is a list of some of the waste in 2021 he has covered²⁰³, and which irritate the author all the more for not only their fraud, but the absolute rubbish waste of taxpayer funding²⁰⁴ they cost²⁰⁵:

<i>“Foreign countries use our aircraft for free for 4 years (DOD).....</i>	<i>\$773,000,000</i>
<i>US bought Afghanistan planes that were later thrown away (DOD).....</i>	<i>\$549,000,000</i>
<i>US-constructed buildings in Afghanistan left sitting unused (DOD)</i>	<i>\$2,400,000,000</i>
<i>COVID relief grant for NYC to display art projects across the city.....</i>	<i>\$25,000,000</i>
<i>Ineligible and duplicate PPP loans (SBA).....</i>	<i>\$4,290,000,000</i>
<i>Improper CARES Act unemployment insurance payments.....</i>	<i>\$36,000,000,000</i>
<i>Constructing border walls in the Middle East and North Africa (DOD).....</i>	<i>\$250,000,000</i>
<i>Free trips for Korean kids to visit D.C. (USAID).....</i>	<i>\$150,000</i>
<i>Grinding up ferrets to develop COVID and flu vaccines.....</i>	<i>\$4,500,000</i>
<i>Tax Credit incentivizing CA residents to uninstall fireplaces.....</i>	<i>\$2,100,000</i>
<i>Translating books into the Georgian language (State).....</i>	<i>\$182,741</i>
<i>Teaching French people about US culture (State).....</i>	<i>\$200,000</i>
<i>Giving irrigation systems to Afghan farmers left unused (USAID).....</i>	<i>\$88,000,000</i>
<i>Developing a film about dinosaurs to inspire middle schoolers (NSF).....</i>	<i>\$2,453,100</i>
<i>Pigeons playing slot machines (NIH).....</i>	<i>\$465,339</i>
<i>Telling people to not burn their trash (USAID).....</i>	<i>\$11,300,000</i>
<i>Funding Green Energy programs in Africa (State).....</i>	<i>\$179,000,000</i>
<i>DC Metro paid Lyft to subsidize riders.....</i>	<i>\$28,005</i>
<i>Attempting to replace an assault vehicle over 2 decades (DOD).....</i>	<i>\$3,400,000,000</i>
<i>Funding the Wilson Center to put on parties for Congressmen.....</i>	<i>\$14,000,000</i>
<i>Study verified that hearing bad news decreases happiness levels (NIA).....</i>	<i>\$1,300,000</i>
<i>Planting trees in New York City.....</i>	<i>\$400,000,000</i>
<i>Government paid for students who didn't actually attend those schools.....</i>	<i>\$2,100,000</i>
<i>Kids crave junk food and gain weight if they're exposed to it (NIDDK).....</i>	<i>\$352,000</i>
<i>Getting high schoolers excited about being airplane pilots (FAA).....</i>	<i>\$5,000,000</i>
<i>Fattening eels for human consumption (FDA).....</i>	<i>\$337,500</i>
<i>Social Security overpayments to beneficiaries in Fiscal Year 2019 (SSA).....</i>	<i>\$4,200,000,000”</i>

²⁰¹ <https://www.c-span.org/video/?435917-1/senate-panel-examines-federal-support-scientific-research>

²⁰² <https://ne-np.facebook.com/TheBlaze/videos/rand-paul-just-exposed-what-our-govt-is-funding-and-everyone-is-going-nuts/308912534667971/>

²⁰³ <https://www.paul.senate.gov/wastereport>

²⁰⁴ https://www.paul.senate.gov/sites/default/files/page-attachments/Festivus%20Report%202021_0.pdf

²⁰⁵ And what a surprise, a simple search and www.factcheck.org steps up to defend these ridiculous projects. Again, the author feels the hypothesis of this paper is more than well defended by their own admissions and behaviors. <https://www.factcheck.org/2017/11/senator-misleads-absurd-science/>

US Publicly Funded Propaganda - NPR & PBS

There is a dubiousness to the need to fund either National Public Radio or Public Broadcasting Services, considering they raise funds from grants, donors, etc. They are particularly strong with left leaning donors, and publish overtly biased left leaning materials²⁰⁶, often claiming - incorrectly - that they are more science based, more factual, not as much propaganda as Fox News, or Breitbart, etc. But, of course, like most things since the 2016 election cycle, there's far too little fact in this. Multiple studies have located left leaning biases in traditional medias²⁰⁷ (newspapers, cable outlets like CNN, etc.). But more importantly, the ability of the left to sense its own bias is clearly curtailed, as revealed in a 2017 Pew Research study that showed shifting left leaning attitudes in the population. So as the donors shifted left, the stories did, and what they wanted to hear, did hear, and their own cognitive biases remained unchecked by the rote realities of fact, budgeting, and that "check and balance" of right, middle/centrist, and independent position. It's an echo chamber. And the funding of these radio and TV broadcasting instruments is significant enough to warrant a discussion. If they are unwilling or incapable, to remain objective and or present all sides of the bias spectrum, do they deserve **public** (taxpayer) funding? And the answer is clearly (probably), "no."

❖ NPR Revenues:

- Private
 - Corporate: 37%
 - Individual: 12%
 - Endowments: 5%
 - Other: 7%
 - Fees to member stations, ROI, and contracts: 39%
- Federal: 1%? (seems more than likely 5%)²⁰⁸
- State and local: up to 10%

❖ PBS Revenues:²⁰⁹

- Private: 29%
 - Corporate²¹⁰
 - Individual \$1.35 each taxpayer, annually
 - Distribution: 27%
 - Underwriting: 20%
- Federal: 14%
- Non-federal Grants: 7%

²⁰⁶ As one of the citations shows, there is a bias against President Trump, and a reference to President Nixon. So the issue is systemic and party related.

²⁰⁷ And this jives with the IFCN table the author shared.

https://scholar.harvard.edu/barro/files/04_0614_liberalmedia_bw.pdf

²⁰⁸ <https://www.influencewatch.org/non-profit/national-public-radio-npr/>

²⁰⁹ <https://www.pbs.org/publiceditor/blogs/pbs-public-editor/how-do-federal-get-to-your-local-station/>

²¹⁰ <https://www.pbs.org/wgbh/americanexperience/funders/>

Republicans, Democrats more divided on media's watchdog role than at any point since 1985

% of U.S. adults who think that criticism from news organizations keeps political leaders from doing things that shouldn't be done

Note: Dotted line indicates a change in mode. Polls from 1985-2013 were conducted via phone. In 2016 and 2017, the polls were conducted on the American Trends Panel, which is online.

Source: Survey conducted March 13-27, 2017. For dates of other surveys, see Methodology.

"Americans' Attitudes About the News Media Deeply Divided Along Partisan Lines"

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

Figure 34 - Pew Research Data on Media Bias and Trust; clearly the "mainstream" has lost the confidence of half the population. The trust, after the Iraq War, was not high already.; credit: Pew²¹¹

²¹¹ <https://www.pewresearch.org/fact-tank/2017/12/26/17-striking-findings-from-2017/>

A declining share of Americans holds a mix of liberal and conservative views

Distribution of the public on a 10-item scale of political values

Notes: Ideological consistency based on a scale of 10 political values questions (see methodology).
Source: Survey conducted June 8-18, 2017.

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

Democrats and Republicans more ideologically divided than in the past

Distribution of Democrats and Republicans on a 10-item scale of political values

Notes: Ideological consistency based on a scale of 10 political values questions (see methodology). The blue area in this chart represents the ideological distribution of Democrats and Democratic-leaning independents; the red area of Republicans and Republican-leaning independents. The overlap of these two distributions is shaded purple.

Source: Survey conducted June 8-18, 2017.

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

Figure 35 - Comparing the Motion of the population from more middle to more extreme.²¹²

²¹² Credit: <https://www.pewresearch.org/politics/2017/10/05/1-partisan-divides-over-political-values-widen/>

The Cult of Climate Change

The problem goes well beyond the Cult of Einstein, or of Sagan²¹³, for that matter. Regarding Einstein, the author and for certain Stephen Crothers and others far better, have already un-deified Mr. Einstein. He deserves credit for the Photoelectric Effect²¹⁴, and that's more or less it. He stole other's work, and didn't give his wife credit, fudged the math, and later he attached himself to better scientists. Worse: he was singularly responsible for foisting the a priori Big Bang upon the world, and also setting up a precedent of getting away with dividing by 0. Lastly he abandoned Velikovsky²¹⁵, his friend²¹⁶, after the 1950 event.²¹⁷ Einstein died before the space age began, so he never knew how right his former friend actually was.

But the cult of Climate Change is a serious problem *now*.

The Curious Case of 'Consensus' Science

Recently the author was involved in a public (online) formal debate. The opponent was unable to understand the difference between talking about magnetism and electricity, but the more serious issue was the repetitious reference to the "97% consensus" claim about NASA scientists. To be clear: NOAA is the organization responsible for tracking this, not NASA. However, both organizations are currently worked by people *not* educated in solar forcing. But they are still getting the results which force them to reduce their claims²¹⁸, clarify, and even question some basic (and erroneous²¹⁹) assumptions²²⁰, mostly about Carbon Dioxide, and definitely lacking in discussion about the politics of carbon (see Table 3). The real fact is that there isn't a 97% consensus (although it is sizable), but that is irrelevant at any rate. At one point of time consensus science said that:

- The Earth is flat
- It went around the sun
- No such thing as germs
- Women need barbaric science to control their hysteria
- People couldn't move faster than they ran or organs might explode
- The Universe wasn't bigger than the Solar System, or later the Milky Way
- Etc.

²¹³ <https://medium.com/swlh/an-ode-to-carl-sagan-575f609a4b05>

²¹⁴ <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/physics/1921/summary/>

²¹⁵ <https://www.princeton.edu/news/2005/07/29/library-acquires-papers-scientist-and-author-velikovsky>

²¹⁶ <https://www.vice.com/en/article/nzzkxm/earth-burned-after-one-night-stand-with-venus>

²¹⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Immanuel_Velikovsky

²¹⁸

<https://www.express.co.uk/news/nature/522307/Climate-Change-Doubts-Study-Shows-Overestimate-Forecast-Weather>

²¹⁹ <https://e360.yale.edu/features/net-zero-emissions-winning-strategy-or-destined-for-failure>

²²⁰ Carbon Dioxide is not an abundant "greenhouse gas"... it's not a gas you'd find in ample supply inside of a greenhouse, to begin with!

Table 7 - % of atmosphere, gasses

<i>Inert</i>	<i>Reactive</i>	<i>Fossil Fuel Related</i>
Nitrogen - 78.08% ²²¹	H ₂ - 0.00005% ²²²	Carbon Monoxide - trace*
Carbon Dioxide - 0.038%	O ₂ - 20.95%	Methane - 0.00017% ²²³
Helium, Neon, etc.< 0.0001%	O ₃ ⁺ - 0.00006% ²²⁴	Ethane - trace, declining ²²⁵
Water Vapor 1-4%		
Argon - 0.93%		Carbon Dioxide

* The fact that CO is not rising linearly, and ethane is decreasing, meaning that automobiles are not having a devastating impact on the atmosphere, except in pollution and mercury, tells us one thing: methane and CO₂ are political and related to energy politics. That means global geopolitics. That means controlling people, not the climate. The politics of Global Warming are population control, and that is it. It has little to do with scientific consensus, unless that consensus is part of a cult that is paid for and informed by select caches of money and policy agenda/control. Anyone that looks at this table and sees massive spikes in temperatures should recuse themselves from the adult scientific discussion.

Whenever there is a consensus in Science, watch out, usually Nature plans to change things up, or there will be a major war (of some kind).

In this case we can see in Table 3 the source of this Consensus is not about dominant gas presence, or PV=nRT, but their relations to the oil, coal, and natural gas energy sector, and the Energy Independence issue in general.

The simple fact is that the Earth has been hotter and colder, in historic, ancient, and paleolithic (and pleistocene) times, and there has been far more Carbon Dioxide, and on top of that, the margin of error in the temperature swings exceeds that of the actual temperature predictions, from low to mid to max... making the measurements (projections) worthless. In fact, it is made all the worse by the politicization being so overtly obvious. It makes solving the pollution and conservation problems very tricky and difficult, when the technologies and Next^{tNext} TED could fix it. It's hard enough, that is to say, without the politics. Yet, the Scientism Cult makes everything much, much worse. People can smell BS, and then when one looks, it is clearly there.

²²¹ <https://www.visionlearning.com/en/library/Earth-Science/6/Composition-of-Earths-Atmosphere/107>

²²² <https://energies.airliquide.com/resources/planet-hydrogen-hydrogen>

²²³ <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/images/5270/atmospheric-methane>

²²⁴ <https://ozonewatch.gsfc.nasa.gov/facts/SH.htm>

²²⁵ <https://acp.copernicus.org/preprints/acp-2021-285/acp-2021-285.pdf>

So the issue, for this author, is that we identify the real problems and then deal with those real problems, with intelligence and fortitude, and no small amount of capitalism, in another paper. The following graphs are present only to illustrate the obviousness of the fakery in contextual less zoom-ins on temperature graphs.

Climate Change Graphs

Figure 36 - Global Temperature based on O isotopes of forams; credit: Open Textbook²²⁶

- The most important fact is not the obvious downward trend, it is that the variability of the temperatures is **increasing**, making sudden rises in Earth's temperatures a strong indicator of sudden, irreversible cooling.
- The 100 kya cycles are notable, but considering we have a new host star, that isn't what concerns the author.
- What concerns the author is that the new star is larger, and Earth's growth rate is probably accelerating.

²²⁶ <https://opentextbc.ca/geology/chapter/16-1-glacial-periods-in-earths-history/>

Fig. 1. Temperature trends for the past 65 Ma and potential geohistorical analogs for future climates. Six geohistorical states (red arrows) of the climate system are analyzed as potential analogs for future climates. For context, they are situated next to a multi-timescale time series of global mean annual temperatures for the last 65 Ma. Major patterns include a long-term cooling trend, periodic fluctuations driven by changes in the Earth's orbit at periods of 10^4 – 10^5 y, and recent and projected warming trends. Temperature anomalies are relative to 1961–1990 global means and are composited from five proxy-based reconstructions, modern observations, and future temperature projections for four emissions pathways (*Materials and Methods*). Pal, Paleocene; Mio, Miocene; Oli, Oligocene.

Figure 37- credit: S. Rahmstorf/Quora²²⁷

- As one can clearly see, the zoomed - in projections on the right are very problematic. They deviate from the sideways trend because of an a priori assumption, a misused extrapolation function/fit, or both. That humans are able to industrialize during the magnetospheric decline is incredibly interesting, but entirely correlatory.
- At any rate, the worse temp predictions probably indicate rather that at a certain level a massive cooldown will be triggered.
- Ocean levels will therefore fall, over thousands of years.
- These shifts are slow enough that no one will die from slowly rising tides, which have also never been measured.

²²⁷ <https://www.quora.com/Why-have-global-temperatures-been-on-a-downward-trend-for-the-last-62-million-years>

Figure 38 - Avg. Temperature of Earth, log scale; credit: Wikipedia

- Usually the author gives Wikipedia a hard time, however this graph is accurate and barely has any of the ridiculously hyper-focused “prediction” curve present. One can see the curve is, more or less, flat over time. That’s what we should expect. A 1 to 2 degree variation, excepting catastrophic events like the Maunder Minimum, or a VEI-8. If temps reach 4-5 degrees above, then our trouble isn’t warming, but immediate cooling. This is well known science.
- It is important to note that humans have existed - in modern biological form - since the arrow mark above. It is important to note that our numbers were small in the ice ages, but expand rapidly with temperature.
- Melted lands mean more land, not less; that’s more room for humans.
- The NWO hates this fact, and have tried, since 1974 to begin controlling the population - not guiding it, but actively destroying people and families - and most of their premises are either based on deep knowledge of the myths or in spite of it, and the facts.
- Faulty guesses are the problem of the “authorities” and regular people will - have - suffered for it. The middle class will pay for it, literally.
- Carbon, however, has almost nothing to do with science. It is a good correlation of the changes, and measure of catastrophe. But it isn’t the source.

Figure 39 - Global Surface Temperatures of Earth, linear scale (millions of years); credit: Open Textbook

- When one takes away the logarithmic scale and myopic focus upon humans, the trend is clearly downward as the Earth has grown and expanded.
- This is surprising to the author, because in theory the Earth has more stored energy.
- The main hypothesis here would be that the Earth's growth has caused a deceleration in rotation speed.
- Quite literally people lived longer (by count) lives because days were shorter and orbit was different; the host star was different too, but we don't know yet if that is good or bad for genetics. Probably bad. But the slowed rotation would mean less transformation, that could mean decreasing temperatures.
- Some will cite the decreased CO₂ levels and density of the atmosphere. But then they would be undoing their own argument because humanity cannot produce enough CO₂ at present rates to cause a concerning rise in temperatures to offset the downward trend.

Figure 40 - CO₂ vs. Temperatures; credit: geocraft.com

- Clearly CO₂ has decreased, and life has existed at all times. Naturally if there is more, there will be more plants and trees, and therefore more animals.

The Micro-cult of Micronova Pseudoscience

There is a black mat (line) in the geographic record, worldwide²²⁸. It is obvious the entire atmosphere caught fire, and the plantlife was burned up, leaving behind a thick carbon layer. The easy assumption to make is that the current sun, Sol (Apollo), had some type of hiccup, and this led to a worldwide destruction. It seems only logical.

However, the author has some problems with this hypothesis. The first of which is that it is patently obvious to the author, based on tilt axis of Earth (22°), Mars (21°), and Saturn (23°), combined with the mythic records²²⁹, Egyptian writings and incredibly accurate (engineering level) measurements there is no question that the Earth had a different star²³⁰, probably for its entire life before 5-13kya. The star Apollo “grew like a child”²³¹ and at some point caused the Younger Dryas Event by electrically stressing Shamash/Zurvan/Ra/EI²³². This event most definitely caused a *vertical* explosion, based on rock art motifs, and this would have left material in the solar system which the Earth definitely passed through, based upon mythic and isotopic²³³ evidence. Setting aside the effect of Worlds in Collision upon temperatures and sand/dust²³⁴ in atmosphere, etc., or the sociological effect on mankind, the main interest to us is the power of the Force - the PEM - upon our Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky²³⁵, and the atmosphere and climate in particular.

It must have been quite dramatic, but not so dramatic so as to destroy all life. The selective nature of it²³⁶, combined with accounts of natives worldwide and mythic records, rock art, runes, earthworks, etc. leave no doubt as to the explanation. The current sun did *not* have a micronova, and the very idea of a micronova is a bit redundant.

The sun can act like a transistor²³⁷, sometimes even turning off its electric field²³⁸. However, it does not need much variability to drastically change Earth. However, overall its variability is not high. Therefore: **most of the climate change variability was due to the variability of the dwarf star**, and not to the current sun’s variability.

²²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9KAsHfeoD-Q>

²²⁹ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

²³⁰

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

²³¹ https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

²³² https://www.academia.edu/70768047/Shamash_Proto_Saturn_OpEd

²³³

https://clarkvision.com/rnc/preprints/clark.et.al.2018_isotopic-ratios-saturn-system-icarus-in-press+doi.pdf

²³⁴ https://www.academia.edu/63468751/Ashes_of_Atlantis_part_1

²³⁵ And the HEGEME

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

²³⁶

https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

²³⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JsfEG4HzWAY>

²³⁸ https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/1999/ast13dec99_1/

Rest assured, if the current sun had much variability, and not a 1:1 Diameter Ratio, and was itself electrically stressed, even as it stressed Shamash, we would likely - almost assuredly - not survive; not even underground. However, radiation levels set aside, the transistor behavior of the sun is a huge concern. Not the least of which is because the sun appears to be rotating around a filamentary structure (as is the Pleiades) called the “Local Chimney.”²³⁹ This type of rotation will have a slow induction effect, and that might cause us a minor concern. But if the sun itself experiences this at its scale, our reception will be much more poignant/potent.

Furthermore, there is no upper limit, theoretically, to X-class solar flares, and a Coronal Mass Ejection aimed at Earth is a well known Cat-8 event possibility. Its probability is low because the Earth has a decently strong magnetosphere. But, the sun is constantly connecting to Earth²⁴⁰, and - one would assume - reprogramming her to the electrical needs of the new Order. It’s ironic, when the Earth entered Jupiter’s orbit, in a chaotic state towards the end of the “Golden Age of the Gods”, Apollo was small (seeming) and far away. Jupiter with its 20,000x magnetosphere of Earth²⁴¹ (the size of the Sun²⁴²), was seen as a step by Marduk to seize the kingship and Tablets of Destiny²⁴³. Now since that ended, mankind has never looked back upon Zeus/Odin as a ‘good god’ and ‘bad father.’ But the fact is that its Force could *never* compete with Sol’s. Sol is incredibly large, however strong the magnetosphere of Jupiter is (RMj=6,344,915 km)²⁴⁴, Sol’s is almost immeasurably bigger. It’s an exponential climb. And Sol is a low-middle class star in a Universe with much more electrically energized stars, quasars, and Super Plasmoids (black holes), which flare with immense, immeasurable power.

The Altstream Gravitation Towards Demonstrably Wrong Ideas

What concerns the author is not only the mainstream cults, but the altstream ones. Some have even (maybe a bit correctly²⁴⁵, but mostly disingenuously²⁴⁶) labeled the Electric Universe a cult. The main proponents are not, however they are far too insular for the author’s tastes. But they have tried to do science the way it ought to be done, and been excoriated for it by social media cultists like Suspicious Observers’ Ben Davidson²⁴⁷, who as you can see once spoke at their conference and made a bid to take them over, live on stage in 2018 . When he was turned down, he went into a rage and tried to whip up his closest admirers in his “Deeper Look” section to hating the EU and laid claims that they - not he - were the cultists. Even that they were Satanists. It was repugnant. The author witnessed all of this in real time.²⁴⁸

²³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BJyvLaNJZE4>

²⁴⁰ https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/sunearth/news/mag-portals.html

²⁴¹ <http://www.pas.rochester.edu/~blackman/ast104/jmagnetic.html>

²⁴² <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/resources/1054/jupiters-magnetic-field-visualization/>

²⁴³

²⁴⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Magnetosphere_of_Jupiter#Size_and_shape The sun’s radius, just the sun is already 695700 km

²⁴⁵ As regards how Thunderbolts fans behave towards criticism. Also <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3fTLZTEE7mU>

²⁴⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vmVdPgkudC8>

²⁴⁷ Who deserves to have his rebuttal: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xxM_uB74Zcs

²⁴⁸ The Electric View video appears to have been removed by N. Thompson

Figure 41 (right) - G. Samuel's Response to Ben's video of 3/6/22; credit: SeethePattern²⁴⁹

Similarly, there are cults surrounding most of the electric and magnetic Universe fans, as well as around fake skeptics like "Professor Dave"²⁵⁰ who make false claims that PEM Cosmologists do not have textbooks. We have dozens of them²⁵¹, and hundreds of years of data and Nobel prize winners. But that doesn't matter to self-appointed pundits like "Professor Dave."

This creates a chilling, and fracturing, effect upon the PEM community, and also makes it harder (as they would desire) to attract new followers.

For example, the author once replied "fake news" to a meme claiming the sun was a ball of burning hydrogen whose gravity created fusion. This is patently false information. However the person normally considering herself a doctor, scientist, and a skeptic went into a hysterical rage about it.

Later, however, the articles cited have come out in favor of the author's position. Though she is not a Qanon cultist, clearly there were Scientism ideas from her occupation (sex therapist) involved in keeping her from examining the facts unemotionally.

Hitting people "in the paradigm"²⁵² is a much more effective thing to do, except that it causes such a gut reaction. People are more apt to accept

²⁴⁹ Ben often makes wild conjectures. In this case, <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2203.07446.pdf> is a paper about AGN SGR A* having a flare event, measured with reversed magnetic poles. It has nothing at all to do with the sun or proving the sun's magnetic fields will flip. This type of wild speculation is not without cost: he sells tickets to the End of the World while proclaiming "Eyes open, No Fear" Can't make this stuff up.

²⁵⁰

²⁵¹ When confronted with this, he simply remarked that we cannot read them, or understand them. It was the height of sophistry in action. Sadly, YouTube promotes his searches even when they are not warranted because of the buzzword, debunked.

²⁵²Figure 42 - Credit: the author; memegenerator

trash ideas (flat Earth, Devil's Tower is a giant tree, humans riding dinosaurs, etc) because they stumble upon them in their innocence when they are doubting the all-too-obvious lies and agenda of a heartless, ethicless (even immoral) mainstream. Shermer and Dave do not lead people to safety, but guide them into the mouths of sharks and crocodiles. The altstream is full of alien propagandists and grifters. While the aliens are a potential²⁵³, *maybe even probable*²⁵⁴, in science we must carefully disclude facts. Plasmoids and secret government programs, part of which we know about, and known scientific effects like the Biefeld-Brown Effect are the type of thing that we must focus on, until something like chemistry, genetics, or hard evidence tells us otherwise. That might be a flying saucer, or it might be a comet or dwarf star whose DR is 1.23 to 1.3.

Figure 43 - Ramesses Stele²⁵⁵; measure it for yourself and see that it cannot possibly be the sun, despite being a stele about the sun.; credit: University of Memphis

Solar Forcing, The Partially True Solution with a cult-like following.

The thing is that the sun could, in fact, vary the climate greatly. Except it is highly stable. Much more so than a star (Shamash) that was likely spiraling around its much bigger boss (Sol) for millions to hundreds of thousands of years, slowly stretching the 'star god' out til it went through the breakdown phase. The fact remains, though, that solar forcing alone does not explain climate change anymore than CO₂ does. The CO₂ issue is indicatory, because of the correlation of CO₂ with catastrophic record and massive temperature swings. But the solar forcing is causatory... yet we see only blips in causation, such as the Maunder Minimum²⁵⁶. And we have enough trouble separating that from volcanic activity, as it is. The truth is that if solar forcing becomes a major issue, as in the sun's variability combined with magnetospheric degradation reaches epic levels, then Cat 6- 8 catastrophes become incredibly likely.

²⁵³ https://www.academia.edu/37856134/Ancient_Alien_Architect_Hypothesis_and_EPEMC_Brief

²⁵⁴ https://www.academia.edu/49955630/Responding_to_the_Cosmic_Hoax

²⁵⁵ https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

²⁵⁶ <https://www.britannica.com/science/Maunder-minimum>

That is concerning to the author. However, what's more concerning are:

1. The swaths of people who are becoming fear-consumed by this because of cults like Suspicious Observers.
2. The types of ridiculous policies governments and elite billionaires would push for if they switched from one bad paradigm and anti-scientific (and highly politicized) endeavor (ie, mand-made Global Warming) towards another. The author wants space contracts, but not at the expense of unreason.

Yes, the sun is dangerous. Yes, it is big and can fry us. Yes it is variable as in transistor-like. But there is no indication of a regular (timed) cycle of destruction! There is a hint of a breakdown of a star, Shamash, and at seemingly nearly regular intervals, but with highly variable periods, the solar system would rearrange. But that doesn't seem likely now. The Moon gets further and further away, so its chances of arcing with Earth again are next to nil. There are no other nearby bodies to induce magnetospheric rubbing. We are the only ones likely to cause thunderbolts, and that's either with machines, or nukes, whichever comes first for China, USSR, and the American Military Empire²⁵⁷!

Therefore, it can only be concluded that we are madmen to let it degrade further until policies are made that make the sun the enemy, too. We have no ability to stop the sun's flares, at this time. Perhaps if we build a Birkeland Polyphase Superweb of electrical circuitry in space, for harvest, we can control the sun's power output via variable load. But we might also piss it off. It's a fine line harvesting honey and avoiding a swarm. One would hope, by then, for mankind to be far more rational.²⁵⁸

Conclusion

Real skepticism is part art form, but mostly it is a scientific, rational endeavor. The art comes in knowing the way to approach the craft so as not to harm future research endeavors²⁵⁹, and when to 'apply high voltage' and even vaporize poor science and those put in positions which they clearly abuse. Think Lord Kelvin vs. Oliver Heaviside²⁶⁰. Clearly we know who won the long term debate, but the issue is the pain²⁶¹, the destruction of careers²⁶², the waste of funding money, the mere fact of the unethical behavior that comes along with grift, corruption, and even vice (that is nothing to say even of the Satanic behaviors!) with mainstream power players who abuse their position and power to obfuscate scientific progress. It is not too late for Science to abandon Scientism, and stop advancing "one death at a time." It can, actually, make rapid breakthrough advancement. Of course, at that time we must be more mature and wise, as

²⁵⁷

<https://www.google.com/maps/d/u/0/edit?mid=1yRfhICowF3RgTw20k2cwjyVbVXWOB0eG&usp=sharing>

²⁵⁸ We are talking, of course, of a Stage 5+ humanity in SPACERS, not anytime remotely close to now. Although strange population control policies could happen anytime.

²⁵⁹ Even if Searl and the Water car, and all the free energy people *are* bunk, they might discover something useful. We must enable and encourage more inquiry, **not less**.

²⁶⁰ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24996836>

²⁶¹ The worst thing ever is when scientists prey on ordinary people, such as the now obviously real Kinsington Rune Stone, in which the hapless finder was hounded by society until he committed suicide.

²⁶² <https://grahamhancock.com/scranton13/>

quantum advancements led directly to the nuclear bomb. But, also we might, and this is a big if, just be capable of handling the Truth, if we give it a chance.

What are we to make of the revelations, however, of the scale of US military and government (and indeed worldwide government) involvement and interference in science? Is it good, is it bad? Is it immoral or unethical for scientists to take sides? Does science act as a MIMS if it enables death and destruction, or if it helps in self-defense? Does it become an anti-MIMS²⁶³ (and if so, what does God think of this)? Does science losing its objectivity relate back to the failures of peer-review? If peer pressure is bad for groupthink decisions, and we discourage children from falling victim to it, why do we encourage it among people many times more incentivized towards corruption? Prizes, grants, prestige, reputation, fame, are all very good reasons for scientists to fight “tooth and nail.” Mankind has fought more brutally, for fare less (superstition, male honor, ideologies).

The author cannot help but conclude that the peer review process, and fake skepticism, turns science into an anti-MIMS, commonly called Scientism, and that the Orwellian control of thought and ideas relates back to this via a complex web of corporatocracy. These corporations receive the support of “individual status” but often behave in notoriously fiendish ways. Honeywell, for example, pollutes wantonly, and then pays nominal (slap on the wrist) fines of \$772,000. Yet the environmentalists do not attack the MIC and PMC, etc. but target oil, coal, and natural gas companies. These attacks are not worldwide attacks but always involve Western companies, like BP, Shell, and various American companies. The hatred for Halliburton is a classic example. While the author did not explore connections between IFCN and media pundits and OPEC and foreign (especially communist) countries, like Venezuela, Russia, China, etc., it is likely no accident that making America energy independent in the true sense of the word is not popular. Many conservatives wish for the author to focus upon the Israel connection. For now, that level of political analysis remains out of reach. However, this paper is a strong call for real skeptics to pay more attention to these connections, and avoid a Shermer-like behavior of defending the powerful, who need no defending. Instead: dig deeper, and ask more questions. Science works best when there are many questions, which lead to even more as answers come forth.

²⁶³ As in destroying of life and its creative processes. Think: war, the preeminent anti-MIMS. Or Satanism.

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